

Validation of concepts and experimental assessment of key technologies

Project number:	101013425
Project acronym:	REINDEER
Project title:	REsilient INteractive applications through hyper Diversity in Energy Efficient RadioWeaves technology
Project Start Date:	1 st January 2021
Duration:	48 months
Programme:	H2020-ICT-52-2020
Deliverable Type:	Report
Reference Number:	ICT-52-2020 / D5.3 / 0.00
Workpackage:	WP5
Due Date:	31 st Dec, 2024
Actual Submission Date:	9 th Dec, 2024
Responsible Organisation:	ULUND
Editor:	Liang Liu
Dissemination Level:	PU
Revision:	0.00
Abstract:	D5.3 reports the concept validation and experimental results of the RadioWeaves technology, corresponding to the activities in Task 5.1 and Task 5.2 of REINDEER. In total, five experiments are conducted covering multi-user capabilities, low-latency and reliable communication, accurate positioning, interacting (powering, communicating with, and positioning) with energy-neutral device (END) , and reconfigurability with dynamic hardware resource allocation.
Keywords:	RadioWeaves, validation, experiments, testbeds, energy-neutral devices

The REINDEER project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101013425.

Editor

Liang Liu (ULUND)

Contributors

Gilles Callebaut, Jarne Van Mulders, Bert Cox, Liesbet Van der Perre, Emanuele Peschiera (KU Leuven)

Liang Liu, Xuhong Li, Christian Nelson, William Tärneberg, Juan Vidal Alegría, Ove Edfors, Sara Willhammar, Yingjie Xu (ULund)

Benjamin J. B. Deutschmann, Thomas Wilding, Klaus Witrissal (TU Graz)

Koen Deforche (BlooLoc)

Ulrich Mühlmann (NXP)

Internal reviewers

Sai Subramanyam Thoota (LiU)

Ulrich Mühlmann (NXP)

Disclaimer

The information in this document is provided as is, and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The content of this document reflects only the author's view – the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. The users use the information at their sole risk and liability.

Executive Summary

Deliverable D5.3 reports the concept validation and experimental results of the RadioWeaves technology, corresponding to the activities in Task 5.1 and Task 5.2 of REINDEER. In total, five experiments are conducted covering different functionalities and applications of the RadioWeaves technology, e.g., multi-user capabilities, low-latency and reliable communication, accurate positioning, interacting (powering, communicating with, and positioning) with **energy-neutral device (END)**, and reconfigurability with dynamic hardware resource allocation.

For each experiment, D5.3 provides detailed descriptions of experiment motivation and purpose, experiment setup, testbeds and simulators that have been used, key experimental results, as well as the corresponding reflections and analysis based on the results. We believe that D5.3 provides a very nice overview on RadioWeaves's potentials and capabilities in realistic scenarios. It also gives insights and guidelines on how to further develop and optimize the RadioWeaves technology.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Overview of Testbeds and Experiments	2
2.1	Summary of RadioWeaves Testbeds and Simulators	2
2.2	Summary of Conducted Experiments	3
3	Experiment 1 - Dynamic resource allocations via federations	4
3.1	Purpose and description of the experiment setup	4
3.2	Presentation of key results	7
3.3	Analysis, reflections, limitations and conclusions	10
4	Experiment 2 - Robustness versus latency trade-off	11
4.1	Purpose and description of the experiment setup	11
4.2	Presentation of key results	13
4.3	Key conclusions	15
5	Experiment 3 - Accurate positioning	17
5.1	Demonstrator Outline	17
5.2	Performance validation of positioning accuracy	20
5.3	Analysis of environment learning capabilities	24
5.4	Measurement 4a.5 - Channel estimation, prediction, and fusion	27
5.5	Joint Positioning and Powering Transfer for energy-neutral devices (ENDs)	36
6	Experiment 4a - Powering ENDs	42
6.1	Powering strategies	42
6.2	Measurement 4a.1 - How to Perform Distributed Precoding to Wirelessly Power Shelf Labels: Signal Processing and Measurements [33]	44
6.3	Measurement 4a.2 - Single versus Multi-Tone Wireless Power Transfer with Physically Large Arrays [34]	45
6.4	Measurement 4a.3 - Experimental Study on the Effect of Synchronization Accuracy for Near-Field RF Wireless Power Transfer in Multi-Antenna Systems	54
6.5	Measurement 4a.4 - Reciprocity-based channel estimation	61
7	Experiment 4b - Communicating with energy-neutral devices	74
7.1	Carrier Suppression Uplink Backscatter Communication with END	74
7.2	Conclusion	78
8	Experiment 5 - Multi-user capabilities	80
8.1	Measurement setup	81

8.2	Signal model and metrics of spatial user separability	81
8.3	Key results and discussion	82
9	Conclusion	87

Glossary

Δ RCS differential-radar cross section.

1PPS pulse per second.

3D three-dimensional.

5G fifth-generation.

ADC analog-to-digital converter.

ASK amplitude-shift keying.

AWGN additive white Gaussian noise.

BER bit error rate.

BERT bit error rate testing.

BS base station.

BTS base transceiver station.

CDF cumulative distribution function.

CF cell-free.

CPU central-processing unit.

CRLB Cramér-Rao lower bound.

CSI channel state information.

CSP contact service point.

DA data association.

DC direct current.

D-MIMO distributed MIMO.

DL downlink.

DOA direction-of-arrival.

DPC dirty-paper coding.

eCDF empirical cumulative distribution function.

ECSP edge computing service point.

EFIM equivalent Fisher information matrix.

EN energy neutral.

END energy-neutral device.

EP energy profiler.

ER Energy Receiver.

ET Energy Transmitter.

EVM Error Vector Magnitude.

FD front-haul distance.

FDD frequency-division duplexing.

FFT fast Fourier transform.

FIM Fisher information matrix.

FPGA field-programmable gate array.

FSK frequency shift keying.

IC integrated circuit.

IoT Internet of Things.

ISM industrial, scientific and medical.

KPI key performance indicator.

LO local oscillator.

LoS line-of-sight.

LPU local-processing unit.

LS least squares.

LTE Long Term Evolution.

MCU microcontroller unit.

MIMO multiple-input multiple-output.

MISO multiple-input single-output.

mMIMO massive MIMO.

MPC multipath component.

MRC maximum ratio combining.

MRT maximum ratio transmission.

MVA master virtual anchor.

NLoS non-line-of-sight.

NR New Radio.

OFDM orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing.

OLoS obstructed-line-of-sight.

OOK on-off keying.

PAPR peak-to-average power ratio.

PDF probability density function.

PEB positioning error bound.

PF particle filter.

PG path gain.

PHY physical.

PLL phase-locked loop.

PoE power-over-Ethernet.

RF radio frequency.

RFPT radio frequency power transfer.

RLS recursive least squares.

RMSE root-mean-square error.

RPi Raspberry Pi.

RSS received signal strength.

RW RadioWeaves.

SBL sparse Bayesian learning.

SDR software-defined radio.

SIMD single instruction, multiple data.

SISO single-input single-output.

SLAM simultaneous localization and mapping.

SMC specular multipath component.

SNR signal-to-noise ratio.

SVD singular value decomposition.

SVS singular value spread.

TDD time division duplexing.

TED timing error detector.

TOA time-of-arrival.

UDP User Datagram Protocol.

UE user equipment.

UL uplink.

ULD uplink data.

URA uniform rectangular array.

USRP universal software radio peripheral.

UV unmanned vehicle.

VNA vector network analyzer.

WPT wireless power transfer.

ZF zero-forcing.

ZMCSCG zero mean circularly symmetric complex Gaussian.

ZMQ ZeroMQ.

Chapter 1

Introduction

RadioWeaves is a relatively new technology for the next generation wireless systems. For further system development and the future potential commercial deployment of such new technologies, it is important to have real-life testbeds and realistic simulators for exploring the possibilities and also investigating limitations of the technology. For instance, to evaluate achievable performance in real-life environment, to study the implementation cost and system performance trade-offs with realistic hardware setups, and to provide practical guidelines and suggestion for further system optimizations.

During the course of the project, the REINDEER team has developed and leveraged 4 testbeds (Techtile, LuLIS, LARVA, LunCH) and 2 simulators (LuSim and TugSim) to conduct in total 5 experiments ranging from RadioWeaves resource configuration (Experiment 1), positioning and communication capabilities (Experiment 3 and Experiment 5), interacting with energy neutral devices (Experiment 4), to system level design trade-offs (Experiment 2).

Now we are marching towards to the end of REINDEER, this deliverable summarizes and presents the corresponding results from these 5 different experiments. With limited time and resources, the results are collected from selected but representative system and experiment setups, e.g., mostly for in-door environments, real-life hardware setup for limited amount of antennas and **contact service points (CSPs)**. We believe the experimental results summarized in this deliverable depict a nice overview of the potential capabilities of RadioWeaves and pave the path for further development of the technology.

The rest of the deliverable is organized as follows: Chapter 2 recaps the testbeds and simulators used in the REINDEER project and their corresponding contributions to different experiments. Chapter 3-8 are the main content of the deliverable, presenting the experiment results and the corresponding analysis. Chapter 9 summarizes the key findings from the experiments.

Relation to Other Deliverables

Both REINDEER D5.2 and D5.3 are from the experiments conducted in REINDEER. D5.3 contains the description, methodology, key results, analysis, and conclusions from the experiments. The content of each experiment in D5.3 is summarized into demonstration videos, which are described in D5.2.

Chapter 2

Overview of Testbeds and Experiments

This chapter provides an overview of the involved REINDEER-related testbeds and how they contribute to different experiments.

2.1 Summary of RadioWeaves Testbeds and Simulators

Table 2.1: Overview of available testbeds in REINDEER and their specifications. Also available at [6g-testbeds.github.io](https://github.com/6g-testbeds).

Name	Array type	Number of antennas	Bandwidth (MHz)	Frequency range	Testbed Level	Aim/Focus
LARVA	Synthetic	1 TX / 2 RX	7000	3–10 GHz	L2	Synthetic aperture measurements for positioning and WPT.
LunCH	8 CSPs	128	400	5.7 GHz	L2	Room-size RW and many users for communication and positioning.
Techtile	140 CSPs	280	56	70 MHz–6 GHz	L3/L4	Room-sized RW infrastructure with dense CSPs deployment.
KULMaMi	-	64	18	400 MHz–4.4 GHz	L4	Real-time processing for communication
LUMaMi	-	100	200	3.7 GHz	L4	Real-time processing for communication, data capture for positioning
LuLIS	16-64 CSPs	256-1024	100	3.8 GHz	L4	-

Table 2.1 lists REINDEER-related testbeds available in the REINDEER consortium, where the key features and the main focus of different testbeds are also summarized. It serves as a complete overview, ranging from Level 1 to Level 4 testbeds. The definition of different testbed levels is according to [1]. Level 1 testbed is for point-to-point link evaluation, Level 2 testbed is mainly for channel sounding, and Level 3/4 testbed is a real-life testbed to end-to-end system performance evaluation. To perform the experiments, as detailed in Chapter 3-8, mainly the Level 3 and 4 testbeds will be used. To mitigate risks, Level 2 testbeds are also leveraged, potentially complemented with the simulations, to perform the experiments. A more detailed description of

the testbeds are included in REINDEER D5.2 (Here we don't repeat to avoid too much overlap between the two deliverables).

2.2 Summary of Conducted Experiments

Fig. 2.1 illustrates how these REINDEER-related testbeds are used for different experiments detailed in Chapters 3-8. Some experiments combine features abstracted from Level 3/4 testbed with simulators for analyzing the trade-offs in different scenarios. As an example, experiment 2 embeds the real-life hardware implementation latency numbers from LuLIS into LuSim to evaluate the robustness versus latency trade-offs for different RW deployment scenarios.

Figure 2.1: Overview of how testbeds and simulators contribute to different experiments.

Chapter 3

Experiment 1 - Dynamic resource allocations via federations

3.1 Purpose and description of the experiment setup

Due to the rich set of diverse services, the set of resources used, *e.g.*, processing and radio elements, are tailored to the particular application. This means that the wireless access infrastructure must allocate resources to specific applications with different requirements. For example, for wireless power transfer, charging resources located near the intended device will yield the highest efficiency. In contrast, in XR applications, the mobility of the user's body in space and the head movement require a high spatial diversity of the antenna resources to mitigate outages and peaks in latency. This demonstrates the need for grouping of resources in a **cell-free** context in a dynamic manner, *i.e.*, in both the temporal and spatial domain. In REINDEER, we introduced the term *federation(s)* to denote the group of resources that jointly serve a given application. In this experimental plan, the 'real-time' and 'real-space' operation for resilient interactive wireless applications is studied through this dynamic resource allocation. In this experiment, the federation orchestration algorithms, introduced in D3.2 and [2], are investigated. The experiment will demonstrate the switching of federations depending on the requirements and position of the **user equipment (UE)**. Based on the conducted experiments, the **LuSim** has been extended to run multiple scenarios, complementing the experiments. It is also served as one of the demonstrators of D5.2, illustrating the near-real-time operation of creating, moving, shrinking, and expanding federations based on **physical (PHY)** layer conditions.

The utilized components in this experiment can be found in:

- Introduction to federation orchestration: D3.2
- The measurements [3]
- The federations [4]
- The optimization [5]
- The simulator [6]

Figure 3.1: Picture from the industrial hall where the measurements were conducted.

3.1.1 Federation Orchestration Algorithm

The following content is described in more detail in [5]. The optimization problem given in [5, Eq. (9)] is hard to solve due to highly coupled optimization variables. Furthermore, its mixed-integer nature adds to the complexity of the problem.

As a consequence, a *divide-and-conquer* heuristic is applied to [5, Eq. (10)] based on an *alternating minimization* scheme. The idea is to alternate the solution of two sub-problems; in particular, for each iteration $\ell \in \{1, 2, \dots\}$, we perform the following:

1. *Power allocation with fixed assignment*: fixing the binary variables $\{x_k^f, y_s^f, z_{\bar{s}}\}$, we solve [5, Eq. (10)] for the continuous optimization variables $\{\rho_s^f, \epsilon_s^f, \tilde{\epsilon}_k^f\}$. The resulting problem is a convex programming problem, since the constraints in [5, Eq. (10)] can be expressed as second-order cone constraints and the functions in the objective and the other constraints are convex.
2. *Federation and CSP/edge computing service point (ECSP) assignment with fixed power*: fixing $\{\rho_s^f\}$ to the solution obtained in 1), [5, Eq. (10)] is now solved for the binary variables $\{x_k^f, y_s^f, z_{\bar{s}}\}$ and slack variables $\{\epsilon_s^f, \tilde{\epsilon}_k^f\}$. The problem in this case is a mixed-integer linear programming problem, and can be solved by branch-and-bound-type algorithms.

The proposed algorithm continues alternating between 1) and 2) until a termination condition is reached. In the simulator, this algorithm runs at each time step. The algorithm is warm started using the obtained variables from the previous time.

3.1.2 Experiment setup

The results in this experiment are based on measurements conducted in an industrial hall of dimensions 30 m \times 11 m \times 8 m, as further described in [3]. Fig. 3.1 shows a picture of one part of the room where one can see heavy metallic machinery, which is characteristic for the environment. In the environment, 12 CSPs are distributed at a height of about 3.5 m and 4 m apart. There are six of them on each side along a 9 m wide central axis, which is about 20 m long.

Table 3.1: Simulated topologies, detailing the number of CSPs, antennas per CSP, and corresponding array configurations.

Topology	Number of CSPs (S)	Number of antennas per CSP (M)	Array configuration ($M_h \times M_w$)
A	2	32	4x8
B	4	16	4x4
C	8	8	2x4
D	16	4	1x4
E	32	2	1x2
F	64	1	1x1

Figure 3.2: The emulated UE positions in x and y, for three different UEs, with the time visualized as the gradient.

Based on the measurements conducted in [3], the environment was recreated in the simulator presented in [6]. In the simulated environment, multiple UEs were instantiated by replicating the original UE in time along its path. To account for more than the original 12 CSPs, different numbers of CSPs were placed equidistant along the two lines that suspended the original 12 CSPs. Each CSP is equipped with $M \times N$ antennas, $\lambda/2$ apart. For the different parts of the experiment, the path loss is sampled at every 100 ms, and is then replicated in time, in post-processing, as a means to make the simulation more efficient. The topologies that are used in the simulation are summarized in Table 3.1 where, for each topology, the number of CSPs, the number of antennas per CSP, and the array configuration is outlined.

The measurements in [3] is done using one UE along one path. In the simulations for this experiment, multiple UEs are simulated at different starting points along this path, and are then simulated over time, as visualized by the gradient colors in Fig. 3.2, where the emulated positions are shown for three different UEs.

In the experiment, the UEs are dynamically assigned to two federations. In Figure 3.3, one snapshot for one UE when utilizing four different topologies are shown. The CSPs are marked with triangles and the emulated UEs are marked with circles. The two federations are seen in orange and blue, while CSPs that are not assigned are shown in gray. Note that each CSP has

(a) Topology C

(b) Topology D

(c) Topology E

(d) Topology F

Figure 3.3: One snapshot of four different topologies for one UE with CSPs marked with triangles and UE marked with circles. The two federations are shown in orange and blue, while unassigned federations are marked in gray.

an antenna array, which is not depicted here, but rather only the locations of the CSPs, which corresponds to the center of the array.

3.2 Presentation of key results

In the following section, the results are presented. First, a temporal analysis of how static the federation assignments are is presented, and after that, a temporal analysis of the power consumption and data rate with related trade-offs.

3.2.1 Temporal Analysis of Static Federation Assignments

The results in Figure 3.4 illustrate the temporal stability of the static federation assignments in RadioWeaves, focusing on the association dynamics of CSPs (left chart) and UEs (right chart) with their respective federations. The data was generated by performing federation optimization every 0.04 seconds, tracking how long CSPs and UEs remained associated with the same

federation, and plotting these durations as cumulative distribution functions (CDFs).

The left chart reflects the stability of **CSPs** within their federations. Centralized topologies, such as *Topology A* (fewer **CSPs** with more antennas per **CSP**), exhibit significantly longer stability, with their **cumulative distribution function (CDF)** curves increasing gradually over a wide range of time. This indicates that centralized configurations maintain consistent resource allocation and are less prone to reconfigurations. Conversely, distributed topologies like *Topology F* (many **CSPs** with a single antenna) transition rapidly between federations, achieving near-complete **CDF** within a short time frame. This reduced stability highlights the challenges of managing distributed resources, where higher sensitivity to load fluctuations or channel conditions leads to more frequent reconfigurations.

The right chart shows the stability of **UEs** as they follow the federations assigned to their respective **CSPs**. All topologies stabilize quickly, with **CDF** curves approaching 100% within a few seconds. This indicates that **UEs** maintain stable configurations over short timescales, even in distributed setups. However, the duration for which a specific configuration remains valid is shorter for distributed topologies, as frequent federation changes cascade from **CSP** reassignments.

These findings emphasize how topology influences stability. Centralized topologies achieve greater long-term stability for both **CSPs** and **UEs**, making them suitable for applications requiring sustained configurations and predictable performance. Distributed topologies, while inherently less stable, may still be advantageous in scenarios demanding flexibility and energy efficiency. Although reconfigurations can be costly, this analysis does not yet quantify such costs. Instead, it underscores the critical role of topology in determining how long a configuration remains valid, which is essential for designing systems tailored to specific performance and reliability requirements. Future work could investigate the costs associated with reconfigurations and develop mechanisms to balance the trade-offs between stability, responsiveness, and energy efficiency.

3.2.2 Temporal Analysis of Power Consumption and Data Rates

In the following, a temporal analysis of power consumption and data rates is presented, including the relationship in between.

In Fig. 3.5, the total power over time for different topologies is presented. It can be observed that the power consumption stabilizes for all topologies after the initial optimization phase. The general trend is also that more centralized configurations, such as *Topology A*, consume the least power due to the efficient use of fewer **CSPs** with more antennas per **CSP**. On the other hand, highly distributed configurations, such as *Topology F*, consume the most power because of the increased number of **CSPs** and the associated overhead in coordination and processing. In other words, the total power is dominated by the power consumption stemming from the **CSPs** rather than the transmit powers.

The **CDFs** in Fig. 3.6 represents the minimum data rate over time, focusing on the worst-performing **UE** at each time step, i.e. which **UE** it is can vary between each instance. The data rates have been computed both when applying **maximum ratio transmission (MRT)** as well as **zero-forcing (ZF)**; the former marked with a full line and the latter with a dashed line. *Topology A* appears further to the left on the **CDF** curve, indicating lower minimum data rates for the worst-performing **UE**. For a target data rate of 20 Mbps, both this topology as well as *Topology B* is unable to deliver. *Topology F* on the other hand is positioned further to the right on the axis, demonstrating higher minimum data rates for the worst-performing **UEs**, making it suitable for high-throughput

Figure 3.4: CDFs of the stability of CSP federations (left) and UE federations (right) allocations. The x-axis depicts how long a CSP (left) or UE (right) is associated to the same federation.

Figure 3.5: Total power over time for the different topologies. Indicating the the highest power is contributed by the CSP consumption, not the transmit power consumption.

applications. The intermediate topologies that are shown (*e.g.*, *Topologies C and D*) balance the trade-off between energy efficiency and UE data rate performance. Precoding with MRT results in CDF curves that are consistently further to the left for all topologies compared to ZF, indicating that ZF provides better performance for worst-performing users due to superior interference management.

To summarize, there is a clear trade-off between power consumption and throughput. Centralized topologies (*Topology A*) are the most power-efficient but provide lower throughput for the worst-performing UEs, as indicated by their position on the CDF curve. Distributed topologies (*Topology F*), while power-intensive, achieve higher throughput for the worst-performing users, demonstrating their suitability for applications requiring stringent data rate guarantees. The higher power consumption in distributed topologies reflects the overhead of managing more CSPs, but this enables higher resilience to UE-specific data rate bottlenecks. The results suggest that increasing the number of CSPs improves the worst-case UE throughput but at the cost of higher energy consumption.

Figure 3.6: Total consumed power (left) and CDF of the achieved downlink data rate for different topologies with either **MRT** or **ZF** (right).

3.3 Analysis, reflections, limitations and conclusions

In general, an improved data rate and lower overall transmit power can be observed in the cell-free case. However, the absolute consumed energy needs to be addressed, hence, interfaces and the hardware consumption of the **CSPs** need to be reduced in order for it to be more sustainable. Another observation is that only having a limited number of **CSPs** (i.e., co-located case), there is not the required spatial diversity to provide a sufficient down link data rate to all users. The **UEs** are being switched between federations when they are moving around, while the **CSPs** are almost fixed, meaning once allocated to the federation they tend to be static and do not move to other federations often.

Furthermore, on the trade-offs of total power consumption and data rates, centralized topologies (*Topology A*) are the most energy-efficient but struggle to maintain high minimum data rates for the worst-performing users. Highly distributed topologies (*Topology F*) consume the most power but ensure higher data rates for worst-performing users, making them suitable for applications with stringent throughput requirements. Precoding strategies significantly influence performance, with **ZF** outperforming **MRT** in mitigating interference and achieving better worst-user data rates across all topologies.

Chapter 4

Experiment 2 - Robustness versus latency trade-off

4.1 Purpose and description of the experiment setup

Adding more **CSPs** with interference cancellation algorithms could provide more robust services. On the other hand, more **CSPs** imply increased latency in coherent processing, *e.g.*, for **ZF** precoding and detection. As discussed in [7], [8], the processing latency depends on selected signal processing algorithms, the topology that connects **CSPs**, and also the deployment scenarios. For instance, the processing latency increases linearly with the number of **CSPs** when the **recursive least squares (RLS)** algorithm is mapped to a Daisy-Chain topology. Moreover, for outdoor scenarios there might be large **front-haul distances (FDs)** which when having information exchange between **CSPs** may require multi-hop routing, which may result in greater latency. An interesting aspect to be considered is that further increasing the number of **CSPs** may allow the use of local-processing-only algorithms, *e.g.*, **maximum ratio combining (MRC)**, which will significantly reduce processing latency by parallel processing that minimizes the information exchange between **CSPs**. In summary, there is a non-trivial trade-off between the robustness and latency when changing the number of **CSPs** in service. In this experiment, we will use an indoor scenario for design space exploration to find the number of **CSPs** that balances robustness and latency. Real-life hardware parameters from **LuLIS**, *e.g.*, processing and information exchange latency, will be used for calibrated simulation.

4.1.1 Experiment setup

We consider a simulated indoor scenario, where **CSPs** will be distributed along a horizontal line at the top of each of the two main walls, *i.e.*, the walls covering the largest room dimension. We will consider different antenna distribution schemes (with the total number of **RW** infrastructure antennas fixed) for measurement 1, as well as different number of **RW** antennas for measurement 2. This way, we may evaluate desirable deployment strategies, as well as overall system scalability. The focus will be put on **CSPs** consisting of square antenna arrays, which favors integrability and deployment. For this experiment, we consider only the uplink latency.

4.1.2 Processing latency model

For these two measurements, we define the latency according to the following. It starts at the time when the **UE** has new data to transmit and ends when the data for the first subcarrier has been processed by the **RW**. The latency can be expressed in four parts as

$$\tau = \tau_{\text{wait}} + \tau_{\text{LPU}} + \tau_{\text{fronthaul}} + \tau_{\text{CPU}}. \quad (4.1)$$

It consists of two main sources, the waiting time for transmission due to a certain frame structure τ_{wait} and the time needed for the **RWs** infrastructure' processing. The physical layer processing latency consists of three parts τ_{LPU} , $\tau_{\text{fronthaul}}$, and τ_{CPU} , which are the latencies in the **RW** caused by the **local-processing unit (LPU)** at each **CSP**, the front-haul that connects all the **CSPs**, and **central-processing unit (CPU)** which processes the aggregated information, respectively. **LPU** includes analog front-end processing, digital front-end (e.g., re-sampling and filtering), **orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (OFDM)**, and local **multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO)** processing. **CPU** is the centralized processing needed for calculating the detection matrix and the final detection. The corresponding latency numbers are taken both from the **LuLIS** and from a vector processor developed by ULUND for **massive MIMO (mMIMO)** processing [9] which consists of 16 **single instruction, multiple data (SIMD)** lanes.

To simplify calculations, a few assumptions are made. It is assumed that the hardware resources match the necessary data throughput of both in-**CSP** processing and inter-**CSP** data transfer, and thus that the extra latency due to buffering can be neglected. The latency due to the **radio frequency (RF)** chain in the **LPU** is known to be very small [10] and, as it is done in parallel for all antennas, it can safely be ignored. Also, as an indoor scenario is considered, the signal propagation, both the one over air between the **UE** and **RW**, and the one between the panels, are not taken into account.

For τ_{wait} , we consider the worst case from when the **UE** has new data to transmit until there is an available **uplink data (ULD)** slot. This latency highly depends on the frame structure. In this analysis, we use a frame structure composed of a total of 7 **OFDM** slots, consisting of one uplink pilot, two **uplink (UL)**, one **time division duplexing (TDD)**-switch symbol, and two **downlink (DL)** transmission. The **OFDM** transmission time, including the cyclic prefix, is $19\mu\text{s}$, and a subcarrier spacing of 60kHz is used. The highest τ_{wait} happens when the **UE** has to wait for six **OFDM** symbols before the next available **ULD** slot. This makes $\tau_{\text{wait}} = 133\mu\text{s}$.

The **LPU** latency, τ_{LPU} , is divided into two sources. The latency of the digital front end and **fast Fourier transform (FFT)** block is $25\mu\text{s}$. The latency from the local **MIMO** processing depends on both the number of antennas per **CSP** N and the number of served **UEs** K . For **ZF**, both the latencies for the local Gramian computation and local **MRC** are included in the **LPU** latency. The corresponding expressions for **MRC** and **ZF** are

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{z}_{\text{MRC}} &= \sum_{p=1}^P \mathbf{H}_p^H \mathbf{y}_p \\ &= \sum_{p=1}^P \vec{\mathbf{z}}_{\text{MRC},p}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.2a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{z}_{\text{ZF}} &= \mathbf{G}^{-1} \mathbf{z}_{\text{MRC}} \\ &= \left(\sum_{p=1}^P \mathbf{G}_p \right)^{-1} \mathbf{z}_{\text{MRC}}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.2b)$$

respectively, where $\vec{z}_{\text{MRC},p}$ is the local **MRC** result and $\mathbf{G}_p = \mathbf{H}_p^H \mathbf{H}_p$ is the local Gramian at **CSP** p . This is equivalent to centralized processing by computing at each **CSP** the local **MRC** result and the local Gramian, and aggregating these throughout the network [11].

The processing latency (based on benchmarking results on the vector processor developed in ULUND [9]) of the relevant calculations are shown in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: MIMO processing latency with 16 antennas per **CSP** and 16 or 128 **UE**.

Operation	Latency (clock cycles)		Complexity order
	K=16	K=128	
$\vec{H} = \vec{y} \vec{S}_{\text{Pilot}}^{-1}$	83	531	$\mathcal{O}(KN)$
$\vec{G} = \vec{H}^H \vec{H}$	946	58k	$\mathcal{O}(K^2N)$
\vec{G}^{-1}	1817	890k	$\mathcal{O}(K^3)$
$\vec{z}_{\text{MRC}} = \vec{H}^H \vec{y}$	81	460	$\mathcal{O}(KN)$
$\vec{z}_{\text{ZF}} = \vec{G}^{-1} \vec{z}_{\text{MRC}}$	81	3300	$\mathcal{O}(K^2)$

In this analysis, we consider the Daisy-chain topology to connect the **CSPs**. The latency of the Ethernet-based front-haul, $\tau_{\text{fronthaul}}$, grows linearly with the amount of panels according to

$$\tau_{\text{fronthaul}} = 0.87\mu\text{s} \times (P - 1), \quad (4.3)$$

where $0.87\mu\text{s}$ is the cost for every interconnection step and is obtained from our Ethernet implementation using AMD/Xilinx RFSoc boards. For **MRC** τ_{CPU} will be zero, but for **ZF** both the latency of the Gramian inversion and matrix multiplication needs to be taken into account.

4.2 Presentation of key results

4.2.1 Distributed v.s co-located deployment of **RWs**

The first measurement is about the effect of distributing a fixed number of antennas into a varying number of **CSPs**. Specifically, we consider deploying $M = 1024$ antennas into equidistant **CSPs** along the two walls extending through the length of the room. The number of **CSPs** is incremented from $P = 1$ to $P = 256$ by powers of 2, while for each P value the respective panels are either squared or have twice as many elements along their width than along their height. There are $K = 128$ **UEs** transmitting equal power, and these are randomly located throughout a plane at a minimum distance of 10λ from the walls. The **CSPs** extend from the **UE** plane towards the ceiling of the room. An example scenario with 32 **CSPs** is given in Fig. 4.1.

All the spectral efficiency results are averaged over 10^2 realizations of the uniform **UE** placements, each including 10^3 realizations of the Rayleigh fading channel component. Fig. 4.2 plots the spectral efficiencies with respect to the number of **CSPs**. Distributing the antennas throughout the scenario into smaller **CSPs** favors user fairness, reducing potential outages for both **ZF** and **MRC** processing. We believe that this is a strong motivation for favoring more distributed antenna deployments, since it increases the overall reliability. On the other hand, in dense user deployments, the latency values for the **ZF** case are dominated by the central processing required to perform matrix inversion, so the most distributed implementation has marginal latency increase over having all the antennas co-located in one panel. In the **MRC** case, the fronthaul latency associated to sharing the data sequentially between panels still has noticeable impact, leading to a latency-performance trade-off which should be further analyzed under different settings.

Figure 4.1: Example scenarios used in the spectral efficiency simulations. $P = 32$ with 8×4 CSPs.

Figure 4.2: User spectral efficiencies versus number of panels in logarithmic scale for fixed total number of antennas.

Figure 4.3: Average user spectral efficiency versus number of 4×4 panels in logarithmic scale. For each point, the computed latency value is included.

4.2.2 Up-scaling the number of CSPs

The second measurement is about the scaling of the spectral efficiencies when deploying varying number P of equally sized square CSPs with fixed number of antennas per CSP, e.g., $N = 16$. Fig. 4.3 shows the average user spectral efficiency with respect to the number of CSPs for the simulated indoor scenario. Aside from the fixed CSP size, the same scenario considerations apply for the results in Fig. 4.3. As one may expect, the average user spectral efficiency increases logarithmically with the number of CSPs for high enough P . This may be justified by the extra array gain associated to having more CSPs. We have also included (annotated in the Fig. 4.3) for comparison the latency values for different P and detection algorithms. Interestingly, the spectral efficiency achieved by MRC is comparable to that achieved by ZF with half the CSPs. On the other side, ZF with much less number of CSPs still requires a latency close to 30 times higher comparing to MRC, due to the long processing latency for matrix inversion. Thus, we can conclude that, in the considered scenario, MRC is much more effective at exploiting the trade-off between latency and spectral efficiency. Further efforts are needed to explore potential parallelism for low-latency matrix inversions.

4.3 Key conclusions

In this experiment, we have studied the latency and spectral efficiency of RW in an indoor scenario with different CSP deployments. The insights abstracted from these experiments include:

- The processing latency of RW can be optimized by carefully designed distributed signal

processing algorithms, CSP-connecting topologies, and the corresponding mapping. Below *ms* processing latency can be achieved for MRC even with large number of distributed CSPs. This hopefully resolves the myth that distributed MIMO (D-MIMO) comes with large penalty in processing latency.

- Given a fixed number of total antennas at the RW infrastructure and number of UEs, having antennas more distributed in the environment increases the system reliability and comes at essentially no latency cost when using ZF. However, we should be aware of the corresponding hardware cost in synchronization and inter-CSP connection when having more distributed systems.
- Increasing the number of RW antennas (e.g., number of CSPs) does not necessarily increase the processing latency. Deploying $2\times$ CSPs, allows the use of MRC, which provides similar spectrum efficiency as ZF (with half of the CSPs), while has more than $10\times$ less processing latency.

Chapter 5

Experiment 3 - Accurate positioning

A **RW** infrastructure holds the potential for accurate positioning. **RW** panels benefit from very large apertures, giving them high *angular resolutions*. The *range resolution* per panel suffers from a low bandwidth. However, multiple distributed **RW** panels can cooperatively recover a great “range resolution” and a low **positioning error bound (PEB)** in general. Particularly, if the **RW** panels are operated *coherently*, there are exceptional positioning accuracies achievable [12]. Eventually, this sets the stage for joint positioning and synchronization algorithms.

The REINDEER consortium develops positioning bounds and algorithms in the deliverable D3.3 [13]. Both are initially evaluated on models and synthetic data. As part of the experiment plan, we will conduct measurement-based validations of the achievable positioning and synchronization accuracies.

A particular focus lies on the implementation of robust algorithms that will provide *resilient* communication and power transfer. Environment-awareness is leveraged to achieve this robustness against possible multipath fading and obstructions (i.e., shadowing) while accommodating a high user mobility. Tracking of devices, paired with geometry-based channel prediction, helps to anticipate unfavorable channel conditions and uses diversity to bypass the affected channels. These synergies of positioning and environment awareness with communication and power transfer ultimately serve the needs of coming generations of use cases in 6G and beyond.

We anticipate to evaluate the enhancement of robustness to the positioning through the Blooloc positioning engine. The software is ideally suited to model imperfections of raw positioning sensor data to achieve robust positioning. To that extent, one needs to model the possible uncertainty/unreliability of the underlying sensors in a likelihood model for that specific sensor, and such models can be readily plugged into the positioning engine.

5.1 Demonstrator Outline

The demonstrator for accurate positioning encompasses two experiments. The first deals with analyzing the achievable performance of positioning with physically large antenna arrays, representing CSPs in the context of RadioWeaves, employing the separation of the full array into subarrays that allow feasibly application of super resolution channel estimation algorithms, e.g., [14]–[16]. Results presented in Section 5.2, targeting realistic conditions in low(er) bandwidth regimes to show feasibility of the envisioned high positioning accuracy of a RadioWeaves system. The second experiment can be seen as an extension of the positioning accuracy results,

Figure 5.1: Photos of measurement testbed as located in medium (see Fig. 5.1a) and large size environments (see Fig. 5.1b and 5.1c).

highlighting the extended capabilities that can be achieved by not only using the direct path for positioning, but also estimate the origin of multipath components as additional sources or targets, all in a mirror source framework as introduced in [17], also used in other experiments, e.g., for position-based wireless power transfer in Section 5.4.

5.1.1 Measurement Setup and Model

This demonstration makes use of the measurements conducted with the large virtual array (LarVA) testbed at Graz University of Technology. The measurements were described in detail in [17] to motivate the proposed channel model for widely distributed CSPs and/or CSPs equipped with large scale antenna arrays. Two types of data set are available, performed over a frequency range of roughly 3 – 10 GHz, collecting channel measurements with a vector network analyzer (VNA) of virtual antenna arrays with a physical size of (at most) 1.5×2.5 m with the actual size depending on the position of the measurement testbed.

In the first part of the project the measurements were analyzed at a large signal bandwidth (500 MHz or 1 GHz) to aid the analysis of specular multipath propagation and obtain a better understanding of underlying effects that might be hidden in estimator artifacts or limitations of the measurement system, e.g., limited component resolvability, limited visibility, or low SNR due to low bandwidth in combination with possibly less than ideal antenna efficiency at selected frequency bands. Of special interest was the behavior of the visibility of multipath components over the area of the array aperture, which is seen as an important factor when trying to limit model mismatch in high accuracy channel estimation algorithms. To validate the performance under realistic conditions, the measurement bandwidth is now reduced to $B = 50$ MHz and $B = 100$ MHz with a carrier frequency of $f_c = 6.95$ GHz (for the medium size environment) and $f_c = 6$ GHz (for

the large size environment).

The model relies on the assumption of small subarrays being usable to perform channel estimation in a coherent fashion. In this case, we assume basic modules of 4×4 represented as uniform rectangular arrays (URAs) that are obtained by separating all available virtual antenna array positions accordingly. Note that no overlap is allowed between subarrays as we restrict the validation to actually realizable antenna configurations. For the respective measurement scenarios under consideration, the total number of measured antenna positions was $M_{\text{total}} = 8400$ in a (112×75) and $M_{\text{total}} = 2816$ in a (88×32) URA configuration for medium and large size environments, respectively.

On the signal level, the signals per subarray s are modeled as the superposition of an unknown number of multipath components $K^{(s)}$ according to the model presented in [17]. For conciseness, we will only include indices for subarrays and omit the possible attribution to different CSPs j , i.e., we assume the CSP subarray model from [13, Sec. 2.1.2]. In simplified form, this can be represented as

$$\mathbf{r}_m^{(s)} = \sum_{k=1}^{K^{(s)}} \mathbf{x}_m(\boldsymbol{\theta}_k^{(s)}) \alpha_k^{(s)} + \mathbf{n}_m^{(s)} \quad (5.1)$$

where $\alpha_k^{(s)} \in \mathbb{C}$ represents the complex valued weight of **multipath component (MPC)** k at subarray s and $\mathbf{x}_m(\boldsymbol{\theta}_k^{(s)})$ is a parameterized representation of multipath component k with a known model, e.g., using [13, Eq.(2.3)]. The **MPC** vector representation contains the stacked frequency samples as $\mathbf{x}_m(\boldsymbol{\theta}_k^{(s)}) = [x_m(f_1; \boldsymbol{\theta}_k^{(s)}), \dots, x_m(f_N; \boldsymbol{\theta}_k^{(s)})]$ with

$$x_m(f; \boldsymbol{\theta}_k^{(s)}) = s(f) \exp(-i2\pi f_c \mathbf{u}_k^{(j)\top} \mathbf{a}_m^{(j)}) \exp(-j2\pi(f + f_c)\tau_k^{(s)}) \quad (5.2)$$

where $s(f)$ is the known transmit waveform, and $\mathbf{u}_k^{(s)}$ and $\tau_k^{(j)}$ the **direction-of-arrival (DOA)** and **time-of-arrival (TOA)** of **MPC** k at subarray s , respectively, which are stacked into the **MPC** parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}_k^{(s)} = [(\mathbf{u}_k^{(s)})^\top \tau_k^{(s)}]^\top$. Note that the **DOA** is commonly further parameterized by azimuth and elevation angles. The vector $\mathbf{n}_m^{(s)}$ represents additive circularly symmetric additive white Gaussian noise samples in addition to possible stochastic interference terms (cf. [13, Sec. 3.1]).

The total parameter vector per subarray s thus becomes $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(s)} = [(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1^{(s)})^\top, \dots, (\boldsymbol{\theta}_{K^{(s)}}^{(s)})^\top]^\top$ containing all estimated **MPC** parameters for each subarray. When necessary, the estimated **MPC** amplitudes can be stacked into one vector $\boldsymbol{\alpha}^{(s)} = [\alpha_1^{(s)}, \dots, \alpha_{K^{(s)}}^{(s)}]^\top$ per subarray. Note that the model in (5.1) and (5.2) are identical to [13, Eq.(3.1), (3.2)], but with *all parameters* included in $\mathbf{x}_m(\boldsymbol{\theta}_k^{(s)})$ for conciseness.

5.1.2 Variational Gaussian Mixture (VGM) for data fusion

In [18], the environment learning capabilities of **RW** were analyzed by means of a Bayesian Gaussian mixture model, also termed variational Gaussian mixture (VGM) or variational model of Gaussians [19], that allows to estimate a number of clusters that represent the location of virtual sources as well as the physical source location, relying on a prior model of the environment to quantify the reflective properties of wall segments. Applying this approach to more generic scenarios, we use the VGM to fuse the estimates of all subarrays and jointly estimate the corresponding virtual source locations and used these estimates to compute the locations of wall segments representing reflective surfaces.

In the following sections, we use the results of the estimated mixture components to analyze the positioning accuracy, and to analyze the correspondence of the estimated mixture component locations with the ones computed from available models. To this end, we will assume that the mixture component with the highest **signal-to-noise ratio (SNR)** corresponds to the position of the target device. Note that while this assumption will only be valid when in **line-of-sight (LoS)** condition, discerning between **LoS** and **non-line-of-sight (NLoS)** requires prior information. This prior information in turn needs to be obtained from a model or when in actual **LoS** condition, otherwise no correct model can be obtained. Furthermore, a “global” map can only be obtained when spatially sampling the environment, e.g., along a trajectory (see Section 5.4).

5.2 Performance validation of positioning accuracy

To analyze the performance bounds, we investigate the achievable positioning accuracy of measurements performed in the medium and large scale scenarios presented in [17]. The comparison is performed by analyzing multiple groups of subarrays in similar configuration. For simplicity, we use the linear configuration that has proven to be provide a relatively uniform distribution over a larger area. For this configuration, we obtain 18 rows of 28 subarrays (in (4×4) URA configuration), thus yielding 18 realizations of horizontal subarrays. The configurations are shown in Figure 5.2 at the example of measurement position 1. Note that in spite of the large number of antenna positions measured in total, the number of available non-overlapping subarrays limits the number of (independent) realizations that can be obtained.

Calibration and computation of the CRLB: To obtain the **Cramér-Rao lower bound (CRLB)**, we use the same method as presented in [13], starting from the **Fisher information matrix (FIM)** of the channel parameters and transforming these to the **FIM** of the position via a Jacobian matrix that relates the estimates for delay and direction of the **LoS** component to the position of the **UE**. The construction of the **FIM** requires inserting the true parameters θ_{true} and the signal covariance matrix C . For simplicity we assume the simple LOS-in-DMC model that was also used in the analysis in D3.3 [13].

As the true signal covariance matrix is unknown, an estimate \hat{C} is obtained as sample covariance from the residual signals per subarray element m after removing **LoS** component, i.e., the component per subarray that was associated to the mixture component with the largest average **SNR**. Especially in the low-bandwidth regime with strong component overlap, this can be seen as a reasonable assumption. The estimated signal covariance matrix $\hat{C}^{(s)}$ thus becomes

$$\hat{C}^{(s)} = \frac{1}{M^{(s)} - 1} \sum_{m=1}^{M^{(s)}} (\bar{\mathbf{r}}_m^{(s)} - \bar{\boldsymbol{\mu}}^{(s)}) (\bar{\mathbf{r}}_m^{(s)} - \bar{\boldsymbol{\mu}}^{(s)})^H \quad (5.3)$$

where the residual signal $\bar{\mathbf{r}}_m^{(s)}$ after subtracting the **LoS** and mean residual $\bar{\boldsymbol{\mu}}^{(s)}$ are defined as

$$\bar{\mathbf{r}}_m^{(s)} = \mathbf{r}_m^{(s)} - \alpha_0^{(s)} \mathbf{x}_m(\boldsymbol{\theta}_0^{(s)}) \quad (5.4)$$

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\mu}}^{(s)} = \frac{1}{M^{(s)}} \sum_{m=1}^{M^{(s)}} \bar{\mathbf{r}}_m^{(s)} \quad (5.5)$$

respectively. Note that per subarray, a common covariance matrix is estimated that is assumed to be the same for all antenna elements. Inserting the covariance estimate $\hat{C}^{(s)}$ in [13, (3.11)] yields

the channel FIM $\mathbf{I}_{\text{ch}}^{(s)}$ for each subarray, which can then be transformed to the position FIM $\mathbf{I}_{\text{pos}}^{(s)}$ by means of a Jacobian matrix $\mathbf{T}^{(s)}$ as given in [13, (3.13)]. Note that we assume the subarrays to be clock synchronized with $\mathbf{T}^{(s)}$ defined by [13, (3.20)].

As the FIM represents the information available regarding the position to estimate *and* the nuisance parameters, i.e., the amplitude and phase of the LoS, we again make use of the notion of the equivalent Fisher information matrix (EFIM) $\mathbf{J}_{\text{pos}}^{(s)}$. The resulting EFIM per subarray now contains all the information about the same parameters and can be summed to obtain the joint EFIM $\mathbf{J}_{\text{pos}} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ for the UE position (in 3-dimensional Cartesian coordinates). For joint positioning with S subarrays (in arbitrary configuration), the resulting EFIM becomes

$$\mathbf{J}_{\text{pos}} = \sum_{s=1}^S \mathbf{J}_{\text{pos}}^{(s)} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3} \quad (5.6)$$

and the corresponding PEB is defined as the square-root of the trace of the inverse EFIM

$$\text{PEB} = \sqrt{\text{tr}[\mathbf{J}_{\text{pos}}^{-1}]}. \quad (5.7)$$

A suitable metric for comparison is the root-mean-square error (RMSE) computed over multiple realizations of position estimates.

Performance analysis. The results are shown in Figure 5.2 for 50 MHz (g, e and c) and 100 MHz (f, h and d), visualizing the chosen subarray geometry and corresponding realizations of subarrays. In addition, the error ellipse for the resulting estimates, i.e., the covariance matrix of the estimates of realizations from the same configuration of subarrays (plotted in blue), and the position-CRLB, i.e., the inverse of the joint EFIM \mathbf{J}_{pos} (plotted in red) are shown as well.¹ By separating all (non-overlapping) subarrays into rows, we obtain $R = 18$ realizations of $S = 28$ subarrays. Each realization is represented by a line in Figure 5.2 with the each dot representing the reference point of a (4×4) subarray.

Comparing the shape and size shows that while the general orientation of the error ellipses is similar, the position-CRLB is smaller than the error ellipse of the estimates. Also note that for the lower bandwidth, the radial extent of both the position CRLB and the error ellipse of the estimates is larger than the other dimensions, with the higher bandwidth also showing a higher radial accuracy. Both effects are fitting to theory, as the contribution of angle estimates surpasses the contribution of the range estimates at low bandwidth values, but the range estimation contribution increases with bandwidth [20].

An important aspect is that while the true location (+) and estimated location (×) over all realizations on average are not perfectly coinciding, the bias or offset is in the range of centimeters. This can be attributed to small inaccuracies when determining the positions of the antennas during the measurement campaigns, but also hardware imperfections, e.g., from the unknown antenna diagram, inaccuracies regarding the phase reference position of the antennas.

Results for different positions are summarized in Table 5.1, in terms of the RMSE computed over the estimates of each row of subarrays (shown in Figure 5.2b for the example of position 1), alongside the PEB and the resulting bias as distance between true and average estimated position (averaged over all rows of subarrays). While the single value result does not capture the

¹Note that we plot the inverse of the average of the EFIM of all realizations of subarray configurations for comparison.

shape of the corresponding error ellipses, it nonetheless allows comparison of the achieved accuracy and the theoretical bounds. For most of the positions, the **RMSE** is well below 0.1 m. For position 4, a larger error is expected due to the proximity and partial obstruction of the measurement position by metal shelves. Additionally, the corresponding **DOA** at position 4 is more towards what is commonly termed *end-fire-direction* of the subarrays, where the accuracy is expected to degrade due to the unfavorable geometry.

pos. id.	$B = 50 \text{ MHz}$			$B = 100 \text{ MHz}$		
	RMSE in m	PEB in m	bias in m	RMSE in m	PEB in m	bias in m
1	0.023	0.010	0.014	0.011	0.003	0.015
2	0.014	0.007	0.021	0.006	0.003	0.028
3	0.050	0.024	0.075	0.030	0.007	0.059
4	0.493	0.046	0.132	0.333	0.021	0.128
5	0.016	0.003	0.027	0.008	0.002	0.024
6	0.026	0.007	0.032	0.026	0.007	0.032

Table 5.1: Comparison of estimation accuracy (**RMSE**) and the computed bound (**PEB**). The positioning accuracy is evaluated at 50 MHz and 100 MHz bandwidth, alongside the the estimation mean error over all realizations (bias).

Relevance for use cases. The performance bounds were calibrated using realistic measurements, yielding results of similar order of magnitude (0.1 m or below) as obtained with best-guess parameters used for the analysis of the initial performance regarding the trade-off with system parameters (see D3.3 [13]). Using plausible geometries of antenna arrays with a physically large aperture and evaluating the performance of positioning algorithms capable of fusing a large number of subarray estimates were shown to achieve sufficiently low **RMSE** to fulfill the **key performance indicators (KPIs)** of targeted use cases. In relation to the use cases defined in [21, Sec. 2.1.1] the results of the numerical analysis of the performance bounds as well as the proposed data fusion scheme capable of dealing with a large number of estimates are of interest for use cases **5 Tracking of goods and real time inventory**, **10 Positioning and tracking of robots and unmanned vehicles (UVs)**.

Note that while this validation was only performed in a somewhat “local region” with one or two **CSPs** in subarray configuration due to the type of testbed, the results did not hint at problems when scaling to wider distribution of **CSPs**.

Figure 5.2: Comparison of covariance matrix of estimates and computed position-CRLB. (a) shows all measurement positions, (b) shows the configuration of subarrays used, (c) and (d) show the 3-dimensional view of the CRLB (blue) and corresponding estimates covariance matrix (red) with the true position and average estimated positions marked as blue + and red x. (e,g,f,h) show the corresponding projections of the error matrices in xy- and xz-planes.

5.3 Analysis of environment learning capabilities

In this part of the demonstration, we investigate the performance of geometry-based environment learning, estimating the parameters of the image source model outlined in [17]. To calibrate the model, we make use of the variational Gaussian mixture approach described in [18], that was used to estimate the reflective properties of smooth reflective surfaces spawning multipath components and was briefly revisited in Section 5.1.2. An important extension regarding [18], here is that we further relax assumptions to more general scenarios and do not assume any prior knowledge in terms of environment information. This requires performing a full estimation of the multipath model, estimating virtual source locations represented by all NLoS multipath components, alongside the locations of the physical source represented by the LoS or direct path. By using generally applicable geometric relations between the physical source and mirror sources, it is possible to estimate the locations of reflective surfaces as **master virtual anchors (MVAs)**, as introduced in [22], representing a more general concept of the mirror source model that enables to take into account correlations between first order mirror sources and higher orders. Another favorable property of an MVA is the global definition of its location that no longer depends on the source location as is the case when estimating “standard” virtual sources. This is of special interest in tracking applications, discussed in Section 5.4.

Figure 5.3: Estimated mixture components, reflection points on estimated wall segments, and corresponding wall segment representation.

Algorithm capabilities. As a next step of the results presented in Section 5.2, we continue by transforming the obtained mirror source locations, represented by the mixture locations obtained

Figure 5.4: Estimated mixture components, reflection points on estimated wall segments, and corresponding wall segment representation in the corridor environment.

from applying the VGM algorithm to all non-overlapping subarrays. With the measurements often containing a number of clutter measurements that are attributable to estimator artifacts or to propagation effects that cannot be described by the rather simple mirror source model, we only select estimated mirror sources with an SNR above a chosen threshold. Especially when working on a single position snapshot, the “correct” selection of the threshold can have a strong effect on the results.² To this end, we select only the few strongest components to highlight the general capabilities of the model in relation to the results presented in [17] and [18]. Note that a prerequisite for environment learning is initial knowledge of whether the channel is in LoS or NLoS condition, otherwise convergence to a wrong solution is likely.

Figure 5.3 shows exemplary results for the medium environment.³ Included are the estimated components for the LoS, and the estimated components for the window side wall (yellow), the backwall (red) and the floor (light blue), alongside the corresponding reflection points found by projecting the *individual* estimates on the resulting *joint* estimate of the corresponding wall segment. With the components exhibiting a comparatively large SNR, also the resulting estimates are well fitting to the modeled locations of floor, wall and windows, see Figure 5.3b and 5.3c. The estimated locations p_k^{mva} of $K_{mva} = 3$ MVAs are shown as diamond shaped markers (magenta), with the location of the corresponding reflective surface represented by marked as \times and the surface normal direction represented by the dotted line. Furthermore, the estimated MVAs locations can be used to compute the locations of candidate virtual sources of the UE. In Figure 5.3, all virtual UE locations up to second order are included as red star (*). At the example of the window component shown in Fig 5.3c, the amplitude distribution over all subarrays is qualitatively

²Tracking will improve the estimation capabilities as filtering of the estimates allows to remove artifacts.

³The environment model is included in the figures only for better visualization of the results and comparison but not used in the algorithm.

similar to that shown in [17]. Note that the results presented in [17] were obtained with the help of an available model (i.e., performing data association of estimates to modeled virtual source locations) and investigated a higher bandwidth (500 MHz and above).

Figure 5.4 shows an exemplary result for the large scale environment. The main differentiating factor here is the larger propagation distance. While one surface can be estimated with reasonable accuracy, the remaining components with either low SNR or an unreasonably large spread in the position domain are not shown. Improving the estimates or selection of these pruned components would require multiple snapshots that are fused by the help of space-time filtering along a trajectory.

Relevance for use cases. The results of the environment learning capabilities are of special interest for general position-based use cases by improving robustness, but also promising for the ones in complex environments such as **8 Wander detection and patient finding** or **9 Contact tracing and people tracking in large venues** where difficult positioning scenarios profit most from environment information.

5.4 Measurement 4a.5 - Channel estimation, prediction, and fusion

For its simplicity and effectiveness, a *reciprocity-based* beamformer is perhaps the most common beamformer implemented in MIMO systems. We have shown that it inherently exploits spherical wavefront propagation and multipath propagation to increase its efficiency [23] and is known to converge to the power-optimal⁴ solution, if *noise-free*, perfect CSI is available. With increasing noise power and thus decreasing channel SNR, its efficiency decreases asymptotically with the factor $\text{SNR}/(1 + \text{SNR})$.

A geometry-based beamformer uses a geometric channel model that *predicts* CSI based on a known or inferred geometry which is generally not impaired by the noise of *measured* CSI in contrast to the reciprocity-based beamformer. An *energy neutral* (EN) device position is practically estimated based on inherently noisy measured CSI, which again introduces uncertainty about the position estimate. So the question arises whether there is much to gain by employing a geometry-based beamformer and if the gains are worth the additional investment of computational resources and power to infer the device position and predict CSI.

In this chapter, we prove that geometry-based channel estimation, tracking, and prediction can lead to a significant performance increase over a simple reciprocity-based beamformer in low-SNR and linear SNR regimes.⁵ In [24, Ch. 2], we formulated our central **hypotheses** with respect to functional features of a RadioWeaves infrastructure:

1 Efficiency:

Fusing noisy⁶ *measured* CSI with geometry-based *predicted* CSI will improve the beamforming efficiency. This is because a geometry-based beamformer is likely to reject physically implausible solutions. This results in high energy efficiency in a WPT context and high data-rates in a communication context.

2 Mobility Support:

Leveraging the outstanding positioning capabilities of a distributed radio infrastructure with a state-space filter allows robust and accurate tracking of a device. Paired with a physics-based geometric channel model, this allows to *continuously* predict CSI of a fast-moving device even if its pilot rate is insufficient to provide CSI updates for a reciprocity-based beamformer.

3 Robustness:

Predicting sudden changes of CSI (like *obstructed-line-of-sight* (OLOs) conditions) in a known environment, or bypassing impairments can enable ultra-high robustness, i.e., avoiding outage with high probability. This can be achieved either with a single RadioWeave establishing a simultaneous multibeam transmission (via *specular multipath components* (SMCs)), or with distributed RadioWeaves jointly beamforming to a single device.

4 Reliability:

Proactively tracking and distributing motion information (e.g., position, velocity) supports orchestrating successful handovers of devices from some RadioWeaves with successively

⁴This is inherent to performing MRT with perfect channel state information (CSI). Please refer to [23] for more details.

⁵For SNR regime definitions refer to [23, eq. (18)].

⁶If and how large the practical efficiency gains are, depends on the SNR, since, in the high-SNR case, a reciprocity-based beamformer is likely to outperform a geometry-based beamformer already.

unfavorable propagation characteristics (e.g., path loss, obstruction, multipath impairments) to others with increasingly favorable characteristics. High reliability will be achieved in terms of both low packet loss and low service outage.

Significance for operating passive EN devices:

RadioWeaves are a distributed radio infrastructure that natively supports EN devices. Some⁷ EN devices are *passive*, i.e., they rely entirely on being powered through WPT and can only communicate through *backscatter* communication. Their operation demands that the *initial-access*, i.e., the first power-up and backscatter communication, has been established successfully such that CSI could be estimated on a backscattered signal. Both their communication ability, as well as their power supply depend heavily on continuous and reliable CSI updates. Rapid changes in channel characteristics may result in an outage, the EN device receiving insufficient power and eventually becoming inoperable.⁸ Since a retransmission is impossible for such a passive device, the connectivity is lost and the initial access has to be established again. This highly unfavorable event may be caused by either a mobile EN device, possibly moving out of a focal point or behind a blocking object, or a changing environment, such as a person walking through the LoS path. Especially for mobile EN devices, a geometry-based beamformer can provide the necessary *robustness* when paired with wireless positioning and tracking.⁹

5.4.1 Experiment and problem description

Figure 5.5: The trajectory measurement scenario in the hallway of Inffeldgasse 16c at Graz University of Technology. An EN device is moving on a trajectory around a shelf from LoS conditions to OLoS conditions.

The scenario considered in this section is depicted in Fig. 5.5. We consider an EN device moving on a trajectory and transmitting uplink pilots. A set of $J = 15$ RWs receives the uplink pilots. Each

⁷According to the definition in [21] the device classes 1-2 are entirely passive devices that rely on being powered through WPT and communicating via backscatter communication.

⁸Once in an outage condition, insufficient power is transmitted to the EN device, such that the backscattered signal level is too low to be detected at the receiving RWs.

⁹Our results in Fig. 5.6 on page 31 show that a geometry-based beamformer can only outperform a reciprocity-based beamformer given noisy CSI. The fusion of both types of CSI provides robustness at the cost of some efficiency.

Objectives		Equipment	
Initial access	/	END	/
Strategies	Geometric channel estimation, -prediction, and -fusion	Energy profiler	/
Energy Measurements	RF	VNA	R&S ZVA 24
	<i>Measurements and comparisons</i>	Positioner	AxiDraw, hand measurements
		Testbed	LARVA

Table 5.2: Measurement objectives and equipment used.

RW is equipped with $M = 64$ antennas arranged as an (8×8) **uniform rectangular array (URA)** with an antenna spacing of $\Delta = 2.5$ cm. They are operating at the **fifth-generation (5G) New Radio (NR)** band n78 with a center frequency of $f_c = 3.55$ GHz and a bandwidth of $B = 500$ MHz [25].

We consider the **RWs** to operate *temporally* coherent, i.e., the phase offsets and frequency offsets of their individual clocks are known and compensated for, and *spatially* coherent, i.e., their positions and orientations w.r.t. each other are known. Hence, they can be operated as a single, physically large, and jointly coherent aperture.

We acquired a synthetic aperture measurement dataset with a **VNA** and a mechanical positioner¹⁰ to evaluate the performance of our method in a real-life scenario. As depicted in Fig. 5.5, the starting position of the **EN** device along the trajectory is well in **LoS** conditions w.r.t. the single **RWs**. Along the trajectory, the **EN** device moves around a metal shelf and enters **OLoS** conditions. The shelf is filled with strongly absorbing material to cause severe blockage of the **LoS**.¹¹ Hypothesis ③ **robustness** of our research is that robust algorithms can achieve resilience by exploiting spatial diversity to overcome sudden changes in the wireless propagation channel. In the context of this dataset, the task is to reach the **EN** device in **OLoS** conditions (i.e., behind the shelf) by exploiting **SMC** channels. As depicted in Fig. 5.5, we model these channels through an **SMC** channel model, where reflections at large, planar surfaces are represented through images of the physical **RWs** mirrored across these surfaces (e.g., walls, windows, or the floor).

5.4.2 Channel estimation: positioning and environment learning

Our **method** can be outlined as follows:

Inverse Problem. As indicated in the formulation of our hypotheses above, we aim to leverage the positioning and environment learning capabilities of RadioWeaves, thereby using them as a cognitive radio infrastructure. We derived a direct **simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM)** algorithm, i.e., an estimator that infers the **energy-neutral device (END)** position \mathbf{p}_n and velocity \mathbf{v}_n at time step n , directly on the signals received by all $J = 15$ **RWs**. In addition to positioning, the “mapping” capability addresses environment learning, i.e., we infer the position and orientation of two walls left and right of the **RWs** (see Fig. 5.5) which we know from preceding work [23] will have a dominant impact on the channel vector $\mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{C}^{MJ}$. The mirror source model in Fig. 5.5 models infinite plane walls through a normal vector

$$\mathbf{n}_s^w = \frac{\mathbf{p}_s^{\text{mva}}}{\|\mathbf{p}_s^{\text{mva}}\|} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 1}, \quad (5.8)$$

defining its orientation, and a wall-point

$$\mathbf{p}_s^w = \frac{\mathbf{p}_s^{\text{mva}}}{2} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 1}, \quad (5.9)$$

¹⁰Refer to [17] for more details on the measurement system.

¹¹The shelf has been filled with absorbers intentionally to create an extreme “worst case” scenario.

defining its position, both of which we express solely through a single point $\mathbf{p}_s^{\text{mva}} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 1}$. This recent concept defines the **MVA** position $\mathbf{p}_s^{\text{mva}}$ as the virtual image of the origin $\mathbf{0}$ of the coordinate system virtually mirrored across the wall s [22]. We employ Bayesian state filtering (i.e., tracking) approximately by using a **particle filter (PF)** similar to the implementation in [26]. To evade the curse of dimensionality, our state vector $\mathbf{x}_n := [\mathbf{p}_n^T, \mathbf{v}_n^T, \mathbf{p}_1^{\text{mva}T}, \mathbf{p}_2^{\text{mva}T}]^T$ comprises only two **MVAs**, but other than depicted in Fig. 5.5 we use their estimated positions to predict both single-bounce and double-bounce reflections at the walls. Using these parameters, the noisy received sum-channel $\hat{\mathbf{h}}$ is decomposed into a **LoS** and up to 4 **SMCs** using our geometry-based channel model. Through the parametrization in global per-infrastructure parameters (such as **MVA** positions), our direct-**SLAM** approach does not rely on a **data association (DA)**, which is commonly demanded by a two-step approach that fuses precomputed local per-**RW** estimates. A direct approach, however, comes at the cost of needing to process all observations centrally (i.e., data fusion at signal level) rather than locally per **RW** (i.e., data fusion using intermediate point estimates from each anchor j).

In each time step, the old posterior **probability density function (PDF)** at time $n-1$ is propagated to the current time step n via a nearly constant velocity motion model, defining the state-transition **PDF**. We use a profile likelihood function which we concentrate w.r.t. the noise variance σ^2 and the amplitudes $\alpha_j^{(s,s')}$ at each anchor j for each component (s, s') , which allows to accommodate the amplitude spatial nonstationarity, a channel characteristic that is particularly significant in **XL-MIMO** and **D-MIMO**. Nevertheless, we exploit the phases $\angle \alpha_j^{(s,s')}$ for a coherent data fusion over all **RWs** to leverage a large coherent aperture of the infrastructure. This is how we solve the inverse problem of estimating model parameters from measured **CSI**.

Fig. 5.8 depicts our algorithm estimation performance given measured channel estimates taken in additive circular white Gaussian noise $\hat{\mathbf{h}} = \mathbf{h} + \mathbf{n}_h$, with $\mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{C}^{\tilde{M}}$ denoting the “true” channel vector over a total of $\tilde{M} \triangleq MJ$ antennas with channel power (an efficiency) $P_{\text{ch}} = \frac{1}{M} \|\mathbf{h}\|^2$, and $\mathbf{n}_h \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma^2 \mathbf{I})$ the noise vector with noise power $P_n = \sigma^2$. We set the noise power P_n to satisfy an $\text{SNR} = -6$ dB using the “true” channel \mathbf{h} at step $n = 1$. We keep that noise power P_n constant along the track, which reflects realistic circumstances (e.g., thermal noise being independent of the channel \mathbf{h} at step n and hence constant).

5.4.3 Channel prediction: geometric channel parameterization

Forward Problem. We employ a state-space filter i) to get more accurate position estimates at time step n by fusing it with estimates from all preceding time steps $1:n-1$, and ii) to predict future positions (e.g., at time steps $n+1$ or even any non-integer time step). Predicting the position, we can, in turn, use it as a parameter in our geometry-based channel model and predict **CSI** for a future position of the **EN** device along its trajectory, hence we solve the forward problem of generating data using known (in our case *predicted*) parameters.

Fig. 5.9 qualitatively depicts our algorithm prediction performance, where we predict **CSI** $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}$ at the current time step n based on the current state estimate $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_n$. We use this **CSI** in a geometry-based beamformer where we compute unit-norm beamforming weights $\tilde{\mathbf{w}} = \frac{\tilde{\mathbf{h}}^*}{\|\tilde{\mathbf{h}}\|}$. In Fig. 5.6, we compute the beamforming efficiency as the ratio of receive power P_r to total transmit power P_t being the **path gain (PG)**

$$\frac{P_r}{P_t} \triangleq PG = \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{h} \quad (5.10)$$

Figure 5.6: Efficiency (i.e., the PG) of beamformers given different types of CSI: A reciprocity-based beamformer using noisy measured CSI \hat{h} , a geometry-based spherical wavefront SMC beamformer using predicted CSI \tilde{h} based on the inferred user position and learned environment, as well as a beamformer given the fused CSI \hat{h}_f .

applied on the “true” real-life channel h acquired with a VNA, and beamforming weights w computed either using predicted channels \tilde{h} (resulting in a geometry-based beamformer), or using noisy measured channels \hat{h} (resulting in a reciprocity-based beamformer).

While perfect CSI (----), i.e., the true channel would leverage the maximum array gain $G_{\text{array}} \triangleq \tilde{M}$ over P_{ch} (representing the efficiency of a random beamformer giving no CSI) the expected efficiency $\mathbb{E}\{PG_R\}$ (—) of a reciprocity-based beamformer given noisy CSI incurs an expected loss provided by the factor $\text{SNR}/(1+\text{SNR})$ in the linear SNR regime $1/L \leq \text{SNR} \leq 1$ and high SNR regime $\text{SNR} > 1$ (cf. [23, eq. (17)]). Since $\hat{h} \sim \mathcal{CN}(h, \sigma^2 \mathbf{I})$ is a random vector, the realized efficiency PG_R (\circ) depends on the actual noise realization n_h , which is why we augment the expectation with a symmetric confidence interval $U_{98\%}$ (\square) for which one random realization of PG_R is located within the interval $[\mathbb{E}\{PG_R\} - U_{98\%}, \mathbb{E}\{PG_R\} + U_{98\%}]$ with a confidence level of 98%, i.e., the probability $98\% = \mathbb{P}(\mathbb{E}\{PG_R\} - U_{98\%} \leq PG_R \leq \mathbb{E}\{PG_R\} + U_{98\%})$. For $\text{SNR} \leq -6$ dB, the reciprocity-beamformer incurs a loss of ≥ 6.98 dB w.r.t. perfect CSI.

We have shown that our geometry-based beamformer using predicted CSI \tilde{h} (— \square) suffers a loss of only 2 dB w.r.t. perfect CSI in LoS conditions and a “known” device position (cf. [23, Fig. 2]). Similarly, from Fig. 5.6, we can observe that our geometry-based beamformer suffers a loss of around 2 dB to 3 dB in LoS conditions based on our inferred user position and learned environment geometry. This demonstrates that leveraging estimation (i.e., positioning, tracking, and environment learning) together with prediction (i.e., geometry-based beamforming) provides a holistic framework that incorporates *physics-based* channel knowledge to improve CSI at the infrastructure side, which yields significant **1 efficiency** gains: An efficiency (i.e., PG) improvement of $\Delta G = 5$ dB means a 3.16 times more efficient power transfer in a WPT context and likewise data rates improved between 1 (no improvement) up to 3.16 times the channel capacity, depending on the output SNR (see Fig. 5.7).

Figure 5.7: Channel capacity improvement ΔC achievable at a gain improvement of $\Delta G = 5$ dB for different values of output SNR SNR_o .

Note that the asymptotic lower bound is found by the limit applied to the ratio of Shannon–Hartley channel capacities as

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{\text{SNR}_o \rightarrow \infty} \Delta C &= \lim_{\text{SNR}_o \rightarrow \infty} \frac{B \log_2 (1 + \Delta G \text{SNR}_o)}{B \log_2 (1 + \text{SNR}_o)} = \lim_{\text{SNR}_o \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial \text{SNR}_o} \log_2 (1 + \Delta G \text{SNR}_o)}{\frac{\partial}{\partial \text{SNR}_o} \log_2 (1 + \text{SNR}_o)} \\ &= \lim_{\text{SNR}_o \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial \text{SNR}_o} (1 + \text{SNR}_o) \Delta G}{\frac{\partial}{\partial \text{SNR}_o} (1 + \Delta G \text{SNR}_o)} = \lim_{\text{SNR}_o \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\Delta G}{\Delta G} = 1 \end{aligned} \quad (5.11)$$

and the asymptotic upper bound is found as

$$\lim_{\text{SNR}_o \rightarrow 0} \Delta C = \lim_{\text{SNR}_o \rightarrow 0} \frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial \text{SNR}_o} (1 + \text{SNR}_o) \Delta G}{\frac{\partial}{\partial \text{SNR}_o} (1 + \Delta G \text{SNR}_o)} = \Delta G. \quad (5.12)$$

Figure 5.8: Animation of the estimation performance of our direct-SLAM algorithm evaluated on real-world measurements. Note: For correct display of the animation, please use Adobe Reader® or another PDF-viewer capable of running JavaScript such as KDE Okular, PDF-XChange, and Foxit Reader.

Algorithm estimation performance. Our algorithm is given noisy channel estimates $\hat{\mathbf{h}}$ with a channel SNR $\frac{P_{\text{ch}}}{P_n} := \text{SNR} \leq -6$ dB. We initialize our particle filter by drawing $N_p = 20000$ particles from a uniform prior PDF $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{x}_{\min}, \mathbf{x}_{\max})$, with limits defined through prior knowledge that the position \mathbf{p}_0 is inside the building, and MVA positions $\{\mathbf{p}_s^{\text{mva}}, \mathbf{p}_{s'}^{\text{mva}}\}$ are outside the building. As can be seen from Fig. 5.8, despite drawing particles uniformly from a three-dimensional (3D) volume, the device position estimate $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_n$ converges almost immediately to the ground truth position. The wall $s = 1$ (i.e., $\mathbf{p}_1^{\text{mva}}$) is estimated successfully after several steps for the given SNR. The wall $s = 2$ (i.e., $\mathbf{p}_2^{\text{mva}}$) is estimated successfully only given a high SNR because it is visible only through a double-bounce reflection. In the depicted performance, we use a tight prior initialization around the true MVA position to use the wall successfully in the subsequent prediction step. Despite the device moving from LoS to total OLoS conditions “behind” the shelf, we successfully track the device even in obstruction via multipath propagation, exploiting the learned environment, and providing ③ **robustness**. We achieve a planar position RMSE of 6.4 cm.

Figure 5.9: Animation of the prediction performance of our direct-SLAM algorithm evaluated on real-world measurements. Note: For correct display of the animation, please use Adobe Reader® or another PDF-viewer capable of running JavaScript such as KDE Okular, PDF-XChange, and Foxit Reader.

Algorithm prediction performance. After a short convergence phase, we can observe that our geometry-based beamformer working with predicted CSI uses predominantly the LoS beam and partially the first-order reflection at the wall $s = 1$. As soon as the device gradually moves into OLoS conditions behind the shelf, our geometry-based beamformer no longer uses the LoS beam and uses the single-bounce beam via the wall $s = 1$ (see steps $n \in \{110 \dots 120\}$), which is possible because the environment was learned. In the harsh scenario chosen, even the single-bounce path to some RWs becomes obstructed at some point, where our algorithm resorts to the double-bounce path casting a beam via a first reflection at wall $s = 2$ and a second reflection at wall $s = 1$ to the device (see steps $n \in \{127 \dots 162\}$). While Fig. 5.9 shows qualitatively what our channel prediction is doing, Fig. 5.6 shows a quantitative performance evaluation.

Fig. 5.6 compared the performance of our algorithm when predicting CSI \hat{h}_n at the current time step n knowing the measured CSI \hat{h}_n inferred on an uplink pilot received at the current time step. This is, the performance evaluation is made at the time step where CSI was acquired. In a real-life scenario, the channel to a moving device changes in between time intervals when uplink pilots are received. While a reciprocity-based beamformer can only reuse outdated CSI from the previous time step $n-1$, our geometry-based beamformer is capable of predicting CSI \tilde{h}_n^* to the current time step n based on the motion model in our tracking filter that governs how the state x_{n-1} evolves over time to the predicted state x_n^* .

Fig. 5.10 demonstrates the **2 mobility support** of our algorithm based on the performance of geometry-based CSI predicted to future time steps and compares it with a reciprocity-based beamformer given outdated CSI. It can be observed that the reciprocity-based beamformer given outdated measured CSI \hat{h}_{n-1} (\rightarrow) from the previous time step $n-1$ already incurs a loss of several dB when compared with current measured CSI \hat{h}_n (\circ).

Our geometry-based beamformer given CSI predicted to the future performs almost as efficient as the prediction at the current time step \tilde{h}_n (\rightarrow) when it is predicted one time step ahead, i.e., \tilde{h}_n^* (\rightarrow), two time steps ahead, i.e., \tilde{h}_n^{**} (\rightarrow), or even three time steps ahead, i.e., \tilde{h}_n^{***} (\rightarrow). This highlights that our holistic method leverages physics-based knowledge and environment awareness to enable resilient communication and efficient WPT even in severe total OLoS channel conditions.

Fig. 5.10 shows how the anticipated “power budget” (in this case a unitless efficiency) may be predicted to the current time step n as $PG_n^* := |(\tilde{h}_n^*)^H \tilde{h}_n^* / \|\tilde{h}_n^*\|^2$ (\rightarrow), solely based on information acquired up until the previous time step $n-1$. In the given low-SNR scenario, our method tends to “overestimate” (i.e., the estimate lying higher than the realized value) the power budget in some steps, particularly in OLoS conditions. This is because our algorithm in its current implementation estimates new component (LoS and NLoS) amplitudes per time step which are impaired by a high noise power. Since these amplitudes are not part of the state and hence are not filtered, our method of power budget prediction using the predicted channel degrades in a low-SNR scenario. We can show that the power budget can be predicted very accurately to future time steps in higher SNR with our method.

5.4.4 Channel fusion: combining measured and predicted channels

Our *channel fusion* (\rightarrow) method proposed in [24, Sec. 2.1.6] probabilistically *combines* noisy measured CSI and geometry-based predicted CSI. While it may generally cost some efficiency, in cases when one or the other source of CSI becomes unreliable, it aids the **4 reliability**. That is, it is more likely to avoid outage due to deep fades in the PG along the trajectory. Fused CSI resorts to measured CSI if the geometry-based CSI is impaired by a mismatched model such as when a LoS is assumed but the device is in OLoS conditions (cf. [24, Fig. 2.3]), or e.g. during the convergence phase of the state-space filter (as can be seen in the initial steps of the performance of our algorithm on the left side of Fig. 5.6). When the measured CSI is noisy and our Bayesian tracking filter has a low uncertainty about the position and environment estimates, the fused CSI resorts to predicted CSI.

Relevance for EN devices: Avoiding outages is particularly relevant for robustly operating batteryless EN devices with *mobility*. After the initial access to a batteryless EN device has been established, ensuring a constant influx of wireless power to ensure operability is of utmost importance. For instance, if a reciprocity-beamformer is employed to power an EN device that is

Figure 5.10: Efficiency (i.e., the PG) of beamformers given different types of CSI: A reciprocity-based beamformer given *outdated* noisy measured CSI \hat{h}_{n-1} , a geometry-based spherical wavefront SMC beamformer using CSI \tilde{h}_n^* predicted to future time steps based on a motion model for the inferred device position and learned environment.

moving out of the “main beam” into a “null” in between two consecutive pilot transmissions, it will not receive any power it could backscatter, the internal capacitor may deplete, current CSI is unknown, communication ability is lost and the initial access procedure must start again. To overcome this problem, this holistic environment-aware algorithm bypasses OLoS conditions via multipath beamforming enabled through the learned environment geometry. Coming at the cost of some efficiency, channel fusion can further decrease the likelihood of deep fades along the trajectory. It constitutes a probabilistic combination of noisy measured CSI \hat{h} and predicted CSI \tilde{h} subject to position uncertainty.

Relevance for use cases: Relating to the use cases defined in [21, Sec.2.2.2] our method is of particular relevance for use cases **10 Positioning and tracking of robots and UVs** and **5 Tracking of goods and real-time inventory** both of which demand high positioning accuracy and high reliability while accommodating high mobility speeds. The latter is of particular interest as it needs to support low-energy positioning possibly enabled through passive EN devices that communicate through backscatter communication and depend on robust, continuous WPT. Both use case **8 Wander detection and patient finding** and **11 Location-based information transfer** do also rely on low-energy positioning where the former demands robust positioning in possibly complex environments.

5.5 Joint Positioning and Powering Transfer for ENDS

Knowing the actual position of an END holds large potential from an application point-of-view. Real-time location data can improve safety, performance, experience, and convenience in different types of solutions. Positioning is susceptible to the initial access problem. Before positioning,

ENDs need to be powered and have to communicate, e.g., through uplink pilot transmission. In this experiment, included as Experiment 4c in D5.2 [27], the *closed loop approach* elaborated in [28] is experimentally evaluated by means of simulations.

Results from the first step in this closed loop approach can provide useful information on the uniformity of the power density throughout the experimental setup when random phase errors are introduced on purpose to each antenna element. In the next steps, the concept is to test different positioning algorithms based on pilot signals that can be generated with energy efficient backscattering communication. The positioning algorithms will be processed on the infrastructure side, to fully unburden the **END**. The Euclidean distances on multitude of locations gives a good measure of how well the tested algorithms perform. In addition, we plan to research the influence of the amount of closed-loop iterations to reduce this error between the actual and estimated position. With the envisioned communication setup in the Tectile infrastructure, the influence of the number of active antenna elements (receive and transmit) used for localization can be tested. The result of these tests can compare the received energy before and after the power spot generation. Power spot widening and **END** tracking can be implemented and tested at a later stage.

5.5.1 Signal and System Model

Based on the geometric description of the radio environment, this section formulates the signal model suitable for **WPT** to an **END** (representing any small mobile device equipped with a suitable harvesting circuit) from the **DL** transmission, and positioning based on (parametric) channel estimation using the backscatter signals in the **UL**.

Radio channel model. The radio channel vector $\mathbf{h}_k^{(i)}(f)$ defines the transmission between an antenna array with M antennas and an **END** at some unknown location in the environment. The m th entry corresponds to the link between antenna m of **CSP** i with a single **END** at position \mathbf{p} and is defined as

$$[\mathbf{h}_k^{(i)}(f)]_m = \tilde{\alpha}_{k,m}^{(i)} \exp(-j2\pi f \tau_{k,m}^{(i)}) \quad (5.13)$$

with propagation time-delay $\tau_{k,m} = \|\mathbf{p} - f_k(\mathbf{a}_m^{(i)})\|/c$ where c represents the speed of light. The function $f_k : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ computes the corresponding mirror source for MPC k for a specific **CSP**, with d denoting the dimension (of the global Cartesian coordinate system used for positioning), e.g., using the model from [29, Sec. III]. The weight of each **MPC** includes distance dependent path loss and attenuation at surfaces and is defined according to

$$\tilde{\alpha}_{k,m}^{(i)} = \frac{\lambda}{4\pi} \frac{\gamma_k}{c\tau_{k,m}^{(i)}} \sqrt{G_k^{(i)}} \quad (5.14)$$

representing the square-root of the average **single-input single-output (SISO)** path gain, where $\lambda = c/f$ represents the wavelength at frequency f , and γ_k represents the attenuation introduced by reflection at the environment boundaries.

DL signal model. The downlink signal at the **END**, from **CSP** $i \in \mathcal{I}$ is a sum of $K^{(i)}$ **MPCs** indexed by $k \in \mathcal{K}^{(i)} = \{1, \dots, K^{(i)}\}$ for the **END** and **CSP** i , defined as

$$y_{\text{dl}} = \sum_{i=1}^I (g^{(i)} \mathbf{h}_{\text{dl}}^{(i)})^T \mathbf{x}_{\text{dl}}^{(i)} + n \quad (5.15)$$

where $\mathbf{h}_{\text{dl}}^{(i)} = \mathbf{h}^{(i)}(f_c)$ denotes the DL channel, $n \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma^2)$ represents complex **additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN)** noise with variance $\sigma^2 = kTN_0$ due to thermal noise at the receiver.

The transmit gain is $g^{(i)} = \sqrt{P_{\text{csp}}^{(i)}}$ is computed from the transmit power per CSP i given as $P_{\text{csp}}^{(i)}$, assuming ideal (isotropic) antennas and a constant transmit power of 0 dBm per CSP. The CSP's DL transmit signal is $\mathbf{x}_{\text{dl}}^{(i)} = \mathbf{w}^{(i)} \exp(j\varphi^{(i)}) \in \mathbb{C}^M$ over the channel $\mathbf{h}_{\text{dl}}^{(i)}$ with beamforming weights $\mathbf{w}^{(i)}$ with the phase $\varphi^{(i)}$ for each CSPs, e.g., relative to a reference CSP.

Note that the transmit beamforming weights are normalized $\|\mathbf{w}^{(i)}\| = 1$ such that the total transmit power per CSP $P_{\text{csp}}^{(i)}$ is distributed between all $M^{(i)}$ CSP antennas. The resulting received power at the END is

$$P_{\text{end}} = |y_{\text{dl}}|^2 = \left| \sum_{i=1}^I (g^{(i)} \mathbf{h}_{\text{dl}}^{(i)})^T \mathbf{w}^{(i)} \exp(j\varphi^{(i)}) + n \right|^2 \quad (5.16)$$

assuming that all CSPs transmit simultaneously with some (unknown) phase offset $\varphi^{(i)}$ relative to some reference phase. Note that such a system would still be termed *coherent*, assuming that the phase offset does not change over time.

UL signal model. The uplink signal received at CSP i when END j transmits a symbol $x_{\text{ul},j} = \text{const.}$ is defined as

$$\mathbf{y}_{\text{ul}}^{(i)} = g \mathbf{h}_{\text{ul}}^{(i)} x_{\text{ul}} + \mathbf{n}^{(i)} \quad (5.17)$$

where $\mathbf{h}_{\text{ul}}^{(i)} = \mathbf{h}^{(i)}(f_c + f_{\text{lo}})$ denotes the UL channel, $\mathbf{n}^{(i)} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma^2 \mathbf{I})$ represents thermal noise at the receiver as a **zero mean circularly symmetric complex Gaussian (ZMCSGG)** noise process. The UL channel gain g in the UL signal depends on the full DL signal power P_{end} generated by joint transmissions from all CSPs to the END and the phase offset $\Delta\sigma$ introduced by the END defined as $g = \Delta\sigma \sqrt{P_{\text{end}}}$. The **differential-radar cross section (ΔRCS)** representing the effect of backscattering is modeled as a simple phase shift $\Delta\sigma = \exp(j\zeta)$ with the END introducing a (constant) random phase shift $\zeta \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 2\pi]$.

Channel Estimation and Tracking. Channel estimation is performed on the UL signals received at each of the CSPs. As only single frequency transmissions were assumed, we aim at exploiting the large aperture of the CSPs. To this end, the **sparse Bayesian learning (SBL)** algorithm was adapted to take the array near field conditions into account, allowing to obtain position estimates of multiple sources directly, i.e., the estimated MPC parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}_k^{(i)} = [\varphi_k^{(i)}, \vartheta_k^{(i)}, r_k^{(i)}]^T$ at each CSP to yield source location estimates (in spherical coordinates for efficiency) of possible mirror sources and the true END position, the latter representing the LoS path. Data fusion of the estimates of each CSP is performed by means of a particle filter, using the LoS estimates to update the END state at each time step. The LoS estimates are found heuristically, by intersecting the source directions of the K_{max} strongest components of each CSP, and selecting the ones that result in the lowest spread of the **least squares (LS)** intersection points of all pairs of CSPs.

We track the END state $\mathbf{x}_n = [\mathbf{p}_n^T, \mathbf{v}_n^T]^T$ in 3-dimensional Cartesian coordinates for position $\mathbf{p}_n = [p_{x,n}, p_{y,n}, p_{z,n}]^T$ and velocity $\mathbf{v}_n = [v_{x,n}, v_{y,n}, v_{z,n}]^T$ using a constant velocity motion model, c.f. [26]. In the measurement likelihoods, we assume a constant measurement uncertainty along the track, identical for all CSPs. Note that depending on the aperture size, the range estimate/measurement can be less accurate thus requiring to use a high(er) uncertainty. Resampling of the P particles is performed at each time step.

The following steps describe the implemented algorithmic approach for joint tracking and WPT:

Figure 5.11: Simulation environment and trajectory.

0. available initial power from initial access assumed as SISO power for the initial END position
1. UL transmission step: UL pilot backscattering based on initial access power
2. measurement step: UL channel estimation at CSPs (parametric estimation using an SBL-based algorithm, heuristic selection and association of strongest components to LoS)
3. refinement step: position estimation using particle filter (UE state includes position and velocity)
4. prediction step: position prediction using constant velocity random acceleration model
5. DL transmission step: WPT based on predicted position (continue with 1.)

Note that steps 1 and 5 also include the signal/channel generation based on the described signal model from Section 5.5.1, i.e., simulated transmissions that emulate physical transmissions.

5.5.2 Simulation Results

This section presents validation results for the validation of the closed loop approach. We make use of a scenario similar to Techtile, allowing insights into possible applicability in a realistic scenario, shown in Figure 5.11. We assume $I = 4$ CSPs at known locations with known array antenna geometry. We make use of the signal model presented in Section 5.5.1, simulating either an LoS-only channel or including multipath components up to second order.

Joint Tracking and WPT. Initial results for a trajectory with $N = 25$ steps, DL WPT is performed based on the predicted position with the prediction RMSE shown in Figure 5.12b/d/f as dashed line, and the corresponding estimated position after the UL back scattering and corresponding update step as solid line.

The results are shown for a single realization of the L-shaped trajectory within a simulated Techtile environment. The simulated trajectory consists of $N = 25$ steps, with the END moving with a constant velocity. For reciprocity-based WPT we use the CSI of the last available time step, e.g., at time-step n we use $\mathbf{w}_n^{(i)} = \hat{\mathbf{h}}_{ul,n-1}$ for the beamforming weight vector, whereas model-based beamforming (*MMSE-pos. model*) uses the prediction of the corresponding time steps position to perform position-based beamforming towards that location as $\mathbf{w}_n^{(ii)} = \mathbf{h}(\hat{\mathbf{p}}_n)$, using only the LoS path. For constant beamforming we use $\mathbf{w}^{(iv)} = [1, \dots, 1]^T$, and for random beamforming,

Figure 5.12: Position RMSE over a trajectory with $N = 25$ steps, simulated for different orders of reflections as LOS-only (a,b), up to 1st order (c,d), and up to 2nd order (e,f).

the weight vector is defined as $\mathbf{w}_n^{(iii)} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$. Note that all beamforming weight vectors are normalized to unit norm, i.e., $\|\mathbf{w}_n^{(i,ii,iii,iv)}\| = 1$.

Figure 5.12a uses only the LOS path when simulating the channel(s) for UL and DL transmission. The received power at the END for the model-based approach (ii) thus shows much less variation along the trajectory, as the estimated LOS parameters are not affected by multipath propagation. The corresponding RMSE shown in Figure 5.12b shows convergence after a few time-steps, and the expected increase in predicted position error after the turn in the trajectory ($n = 16$), with a position RMSE below 0.1 m for most part of the trajectory. Figure 5.12c simulates up to first order reflections in the signal transmission, which results in stronger fluctuations of the power received at the END, as well as an increase in the RMSE of the END position shown in Figure 5.12d. Including up to second order reflections results in stronger notches for the power received at the END (see Figure 5.12e). While the convergence speed to a stable level of RMSE is seemingly unaffected by the simulated maximum reflection order, the RMSE generally increases with order of reflections.

Relevance for use cases: This simulation-based validation of the proposed closed loop approach serves as proof of concept of the advantages of model-based approaches for joint tracking and WPT. Relating to the use cases defined in [21, Sec. 2.2.2], this is of special interest to use cases **5** *Tracking of goods and real-time inventory* and **6** *Electronic labelling* where **ENDs** are expected to be widely used.

Chapter 6

Experiment 4a - Powering ENDS

6.1 Powering strategies

A wireless infrastructure operating fully passive EN devices faces the initial access problem: When it is put into operation for the first time, it aims to communicate with EN devices and supply them with power wirelessly. Different strategies are experimentally investigated to perform WPT to the ENDS, *i.e.*, through:

1. reciprocity-based beamforming,
2. geometry-based beamforming,
3. codebook-based beamforming,
4. random-phased charging.

As reciprocity-based beamforming (strategy 1), obtained through sending uplink pilots, is unavailable before the initial wake-up of an EN device, geometry-based (strategy 2), *i.e.*, *predicted CSI* can be used to overcome this problem by predicting channels from a known geometry, *i.e.*, known positions of RWs panels and EN devices. Unfortunately, the position p of an EN device cannot always be assumed known, which adds to the complexity of the initial access problem. To compensate for a possibly unknown position p , a *beam sweep* can be conducted, *i.e.*, a space of possible positions p can be searched iteratively until the initial wakeup of the EN device. It should be noted that geometry-based channel prediction demands a known geometry (including the array layout) and also a phase-calibrated array, *i.e.*, the phases at all antennas within one array need to be aligned. Other approaches like (exhaustive) codebook-based beamforming (strategy 3), or random-phased charging (strategy 4) do not demand geometric knowledge or phase-calibrated arrays. The former can achieve good performance if iterated through an exhaustive codebook, but the codebook search becomes prohibitive in mMIMO applications due to the large codebook sizes. The latter approach, *i.e.*, random-phased charging (strategy 4) can be utilised to slowly charge devices, only for initial access without knowing their location. After being charged, a pilot can be sent to enable positioning and reciprocity-based beamforming.

6.1.1 Geometry-based WPT.

In [30], the REINDEER consortium has used the TugSim simulator to show how *beam diversity* can be used to overcome impairments in the initial access introduced by an environment

with strong multipath propagation. In [28], the LARVA testbed was used to demonstrate how geometry-based beamformers can be used to solve the initial access problem. A variety of geometry-based beamformers have been tested on synthetic aperture measurements acquired with the LARVA testbed. Furthermore, a random (opportunistic) beamformer has been explored using the TugSim simulator to solve the initial access problem and a closed-loop approach has been implemented, which iteratively performs positioning and geometry-based beamform.

The deliverable D4.2 [28] represents a foundation for exploiting geometry-based predicted CSI for the initial access procedure. So far, a complete exhaustive beam sweep has been performed only with a simple planar wavefront beamformer. Conducting exhaustive beam sweeps with spherical wavefront beamformers may be costly both in terms of time and energy. As part of the experiment plan, particularly with respect to [31], the REINDEER consortium will investigate different beam sweeping schemes that will reduce sweep times and overcome problems associated with exhaustive beam sweeps.

In realistic scenarios, we will demonstrate how close we can get to these upper limits for power budgets. Using synthetic aperture measurements, we demonstrated that a (40×25) -URA transmitting 1 W of power at an operating at 3.79 GHz is capable to supply more than 1 mW of power to an EN device located at a distance of 12.3 m [23]. Lifting the receivable powers from the microwatt to the milliwatt region is a feature that a RadioWeaves infrastructure achieves through physically large apertures with massive, distributed antennas, and operating at sub-10 GHz frequencies. These are distinguishing characteristics in an era where most 6G research seeks to explore very high frequency ranges from the mmWave up to THz bands.

6.1.2 Random-phased WPT.

In addition to geometry-based WPT, random phased WPT can be used to charge ENs initially. This approach reduces the exploration space to search for devices, resulting in a more scalable method. Furthermore, this method does not impose that the infrastructure needs to operate coherently. Hence, it can be used before or during phase calibration of the network.

6.1.3 Power budgets for EN devices

In deliverable D4.1 [32], the REINDEER consortium has examined the achievable power budgets of a RW deployment with respect to regulatory constraints. A major finding of the analysis was that WPT benefits from physically large or distributed radio architectures, both in terms of high efficiencies through large apertures and regulatory compliance through spatially low power densities. Given that the RW infrastructure is distributed reasonably well with respect to the EN device, it may be possible to generate a focal region attaining the maximum regulatory-compliant power density while exhibiting lower power densities everywhere else. Based on that assumption, the REINDEER consortium proposed power budgets achievable with isotropic antennas at different sub-10 GHz frequencies [32, Table 4.1]. We demonstrate that the extra-large MIMO (XL-MIMO) measurements in [23] suffice the mentioned requirements, and an EN device located at a distance of 12.3 m can be supplied with a power close to that stated in the deliverable D4.1.

6.1.4 Outline of this chapter

The following sections of this chapter discusses the experiments related to powering energy-neutral devices. Table 6.1 provides a brief overview of the measurements. Note that Measure-

ment 4a.5 is included in Chapter 5 as Section 5.4 due to the close connection with positioning and environment learning.

Measurement 4a.1	Optimization problem focused on reducing infrastructure energy consumption , validated by measurements.	Sec. 6.2
Measurement 4a.2	Optimal strategy for delivering an initial amount of energy to a depleted END and estimating response time.	Sec. 6.3
Measurement 4a.3	Comparison of measurement results for the strategies Random-phased WPT and Reciprocity-based Beamforming .	Sec. 6.4
Measurement 4a.4	Reciprocity-based channel estimation.	Sec. 6.5
Measurement 4a.5	Comparison of measurement results for Geometry-based Beamforming and Reciprocity-based Beamforming.	Sec. 5.4

Table 6.1: Overview of conducted measurements and corresponding sections.

6.2 Measurement 4a.1 - How to Perform Distributed Precoding to Wirelessly Power Shelf Labels: Signal Processing and Measurements [33]

WPT has garnered increasing attention due to its potential to eliminate device-side batteries. With the advent of **D-MIMO**, **RF WPT** has become feasible over extended distances. This study focuses on optimizing the energy delivery to **Energy Receivers (ERs)** while minimizing system’s total transmit power. Rather than continuous power delivery, we optimize the precoding weights within specified time slots to meet the energy requirements of the **ERs**. Both unsynchronized (non-coherent) and synchronized (coherent) systems are evaluated. Experimental validation was conducted using a testbed with 84 antennas, validating the trends observed in our numerical simulations.

Table 6.2: Measurement objectives and equipment used.

Objectives		Equipment	
Initial access	/	END	/
Strategies	Random-phased WPT and Beamforming (not specified)	Energy profiler	/
Energy Measurements	RF	Spectrum analyzer	Scope MSO64B
<i>Optimization problem and measurements</i>		Positioner	Qualisys
		Testbed	Techtile

Contributions and Findings: Our analysis indicates that augmenting the number of antennas and transitioning from an unsynchronized to a synchronized full phase-coherent system substantially enhances system performance. This optimization ensures precise energy delivery, reducing overshoots and overall energy consumption.

Figure 6.1: Illustration of a distributed WPT system, where several Energy Transmitters (ETs) transmit signals over M antennas to K ERs to charge them over N time slots. In this example, during slot n only ER k is targeted, while at $n + 1$ ER $_0$ and ER $_{K-1}$ is being charged.

6.3 Measurement 4a.2 - Single versus Multi-Tone Wireless Power Transfer with Physically Large Arrays [34]

Distributed beamforming is a key enabler to provide power wirelessly to a massive amount of ENDS. However, without prior information and fully depleted ENDS, initially powering these devices efficiently is an open question. These measurements investigate and assess the feasibility of harvesting sufficient energy to transmit a backscatter pilot signal from the END, which can be then used for coherent downlink transmission. We experimentally evaluated adaptive single-tone and multi-tone signals during initial charging. The results indicate that the response time for ENDS with unknown locations can extend to several tens of seconds. Notably, the adaptive single-tone excitation shows, among others, better performance at lower transmit power levels, providing a faster response. These findings underscore the potential of adaptive single-tone signals in optimizing power delivery to END in future networks.

Table 6.3: Measurement objectives and equipment used.

Objectives		Equipment	
Initial access	yes	END	Only for power data
Strategies	Random-phased WPT	Energy profiler	KUL EP
Energy Measurements	RF and DC	Spectrum analyzer	Scope MSO64B
		Positioner	Qualisys
<i>Measurements and estimations</i>		Testbed	Techtile

Contributions and Findings:

In this study, we experimentally determine the most effective strategy for initially charging a real END without prior knowledge of its location and with a depleted energy supply. The considered operation is depicted in Figure 6.2. A custom-developed energy profiler (EP) utilizes a state-of-the-art energy harvesting test IC from NXP. We compare the performance of single-tone and multi-tone transmissions using an 84-antenna system. Our experiments demonstrate that adaptive single-tone transmission outperforms multi-tone waveforms across all key metrics: har-

Figure 6.2: Considered three-phase operation: 1) non-coherent downlink WPT (left), 2) 10-byte uplink pilot transmission (middle) and 3) reciprocity-based coherent downlink WPT (right). This work focuses on the two first phases.

Figure 6.3: Illustration of the real-life testbed [36] and energy profiler's location.

vester efficiency (RF-to-DC conversion), probability of achieving the required **microcontroller unit (MCU)** voltage, and uplink pilot response time. This indicates that single-tone transmission enables **ENDs** to receive more energy and wake up faster compared to multi-tone signals for initial access. The design files, along with details about the experiment and the collected data, are available in the [GitHub](#) repository [35].

6.3.1 Large Array, Energy-Neutral Device and Energy Profiler

Performing an empirical comparison between several transmit signals involves numerous hardware and software requirements. This section outlines the developments necessary for conducting practical measurements. Some components are not commercially available and were specifically developed for this work. A flexible and configurable infrastructure is crucial, incorporating large arrays as introduced in Section 6.3.1.1. Additionally, an energy-neutral device implementation is required to determine the necessary energy and energy buffer size, as detailed in Section 6.3.1.2. Finally, an **EP** is essential for performing RF-to-DC conversion and measuring the received **direct current (DC)** energy, as explained in Section 6.3.1.3.

6.3.1.1 Large Array

The measurements described in Section 6.3.2 are performed with the Tectile testbed [36]. Only parts of the infrastructure are used in this work, specifically the antennas located in the ceiling.

Figure 6.4: Hardware architectures. The transparent blocks of the END architecture were not considered during the analysis, as the primary goal was to measure the power consumption of the MCU and the RF switch.

The setup involves 84 antennas paired with 42 universal software radio peripheral (USRP) B210 devices. Control of the USRPs is managed by 42 Raspberry Pis (RPIs) units, which are connected to the local network of the Techtile testbed. The testbed is time and frequency synchronised, given that multiple USRPs could generate exactly the same frequency from a shared 10 MHz clock source. As a result, the relative phase between two frequency synchronous USRPs is constant over time. The dimensions of the testbed are illustrated in Figure 6.3, and a more detailed discussion of the testbed can be found in [36].

6.3.1.2 Energy-Neutral Device and Energy Buffer Requirements

For coherent downlink wireless power beamforming, the infrastructure, here in form of a large array, requires CSI. In order to obtain this, the END can use backscattering. The objective of this section is to determine the energy needed at the END side to backscatter a pilot signal and, additionally, to ascertain the size of the buffer capacitor.

We consider an embedded device with only backscatter capabilities, as detailed in Figure 6.4a. A low-power MCU uses one of its internal timers to control an external RF switch. The RF switch is located just behind the antenna, allowing it to change the impedance between the harvester impedance and a short-circuit termination.

The timer divides the 1.024 MHz clock by two, to provide a 512 kHz local oscillator (LO) offset to the RF switch and therefore prevents interference with the carrier wave. A second timer modulates information at a baud rate of 1 kbit s^{-1} by controlling the first timer. We assume a pilot message of 10 bytes¹. Consequently, it takes 80 ms to backscatter 10 bytes of data. The MCU, powered at 1.8 V, consumes $380 \mu\text{W}$ during operation. Thus, the energy demand of the MCU E_{MCU} amounts $30.4 \mu\text{J}$. The data in the message being backscattered is not of interest in this work.

The MCU starts executing instructions once the voltage exceeds the threshold value $V_{\text{MCU}_{th}}$ of 1.75 V and stops executing instructions when the supply voltage drops below the brown-out threshold V_{BOD} value of 1.55 V. Subsequently, the buffer capacitor C_B can be calculated using

¹ Although the pilot length determines the number of ENDS that can be potentially multiplexed, here we do not target simultaneous uplink pilot transmission. Actually, the hypothesis is that using adaptive single carrier transmission, ENDS will awake at different time instances, mitigating pilot contamination. Hence, the pilot length only has an effect on the channel estimate quality, which does not affect the findings and conclusions of this work.

$$C_B = \frac{2E_{MCU}}{V_{MCU_{th}}^2 - V_{BOD}^2}. \quad (6.1)$$

Inserting the values from above results in a minimum buffer capacitance requirement of $92 \mu\text{F}$, which means a capacitance of $100 \mu\text{F}$ should be sufficient to send the pilot message for the considered **END** architecture (Figure 6.4a).

6.3.1.3 Energy Profiler

To achieve accurate **DC** power measurements that account for nonlinearities and threshold voltage levels, we have developed and implemented an **energy profiler (EP)**. The **EP** incorporates several features to validate and optimize the performance of **radio frequency power transfer (RFPT)** systems. It includes a tuning network that enhances impedance matching with antennas having a characteristic impedance of 50Ω . The system features an energy harvester that converts RF signals into **DC** energy [37], capable of providing a maximum output voltage of 2 V , without damaging the internal charge pump circuits. This voltage level should be sufficient to reliably power **MCUs**, as discussed earlier in Section 6.3.1.2. Additionally, the profiler integrates precise power measurement capabilities using a programmable potentiometer and a high-resolution 16-bit **analog-to-digital converter (ADC)**. This setup allows for accurate monitoring of power levels, crucial for evaluating energy harvesting efficiency. Operating at a sample rate and control loop speed of 1 kHz , the **EP** ensures rapid response times and precise control in dynamic environments. Furthermore, the **EP** offers an adjustable target voltage feature, enabling users to simulate real-life conditions accurately. This flexibility is essential, as **MCUs** typically require a minimum input voltage of approximately 1.8 V for stable operation. By adjusting the target voltage, the **EP** can simulate varying operating conditions to validate performance under different scenarios effectively.

6.3.2 Measurement Campaign

Our objective is to achieve a rapid response time (phase 2 in Figure 6.2) from the **END**, ensuring that it transmits its pilot message as promptly as possible. Additionally, we seek to accomplish this with minimal overall transmit power from the infrastructure. Three key questions need to be addressed to optimize this process: What is the optimal signal type to apply? How should the **USRPs** be configured? What is the required transmit power per antenna? These questions will be systematically explored through measurements in this section and the subsequent one.

6.3.2.1 Measurement Setup

We consider the infrastructure depicted in Figure 6.3, where the ceiling antennas are utilized for the measurements. In the measurement setup, the receiver has two antennas to compare the harvested **DC** power with the RF channel power, as shown in Figure 6.5. The **EP** connected to the right antenna and explained in Section 6.3.1.3, forwards the **DC** power and **DC** voltage values to a central computer at a sample rate of 250 Hz . The target voltage is set to 1.8 V with an accuracy of 50 mV , meaning that the internal regulator does not adjust the programmable load, if the harvester voltage is within the interval $[1.75, 1.85] \text{ V}$. Simultaneously, the RF channel power is measured with the left antenna and an MSO64B oscilloscope (6 GHz bandwidth) at a sample rate of approximately 20 Hz .

Figure 6.5: Picture of the receive side of the measurement setup, showing two half-wavelength antennas and the energy profiler.

Furthermore, the measurement instruments, **RPis**, and **USRPs** are controlled by a central computing system. This system reconfigures the infrastructure for each measurement session and ensures storage of the obtained data.

6.3.3 Conducted Measurements

The **USRPs** of Techtile can be configured in various ways. In this paper, we focus on two relevant configurations of the infrastructure:

Meas 1 All transmitters are frequency synchronized and configured to transmit at the same frequency, i.e., 920 MHz. To avoid the possibility of an **END** being located in an area of destructive interference, the phases are adjusted periodically, i.e., adaptive single-tone transmission. In this work, the phase of each antenna is randomly changed every 5 seconds.

Meas 2 The harvester's bandwidth spans several MHz, allowing it to harvest frequency components adjacent to the center frequency of 920 MHz. Consequently, a second configuration involves generating an equally-spaced multi-tone excitation by assigning individual frequencies to each antenna. Here, a frequency offset of 100 Hz is used. Using 84 antennas, this equates to 84 carriers, spanning a bandwidth of 8.4 kHz.²

Since the **END**'s location is often unknown in real-world scenarios, all antennas are configured with the same gain setting for each **USRP**. If the location were known, an optimization algorithm could be employed to efficiently transfer the initial energy to the **END**, as proposed in [33] (??).

The transmit gain of the 84 antennas is swept from 75 dB to 85 dB in 1 dB increments, corresponding to a real output power range of 9.1 to 17.4 dBm per antenna. This varying gain is expected to demonstrate the nonlinearities of the harvester, allowing to determine the required gain (or

²In contrast to other work, our setup uses single carrier transmission per antenna resulting in a received signal with frequency fading due to different channels between the distributed transmit antennas and the **END** even though a narrowband signal is transmitted.

equivalently transmit power) necessary to provide sufficient initial energy to the **END**. In total, 11 gain configurations are tested per measurement, each with a duration of 30 minutes.

All measurements are conducted at a static location (Figure 6.3). It is important to note that the locations of the two antennas are not identical, thus the antennas will experience different small-scale fading. However, the average received RF and **DC** powers are still relevant for comparison purposes, as discussed in Section 6.3.4. The location of the receiver in our measurement setup remained unchanged in this study (Figure 6.3).

6.3.4 Data Processing and Discussion

In this section, we demonstrate that for the same amount of radiated power, single-tone excitation yields better harvester efficiency and increases the likelihood of receiving a response. A detailed discussion is provided in this section.

6.3.4.1 Average RF/DC Energy and Harvester Efficiency

Due to the distance between the scope and **EP** antenna, the received power is different at both locations due to small-scale fading effects, as previously mentioned in Section 6.3.3. For each individual measurement, such as those shown in Figures 6.7a and 6.7b, the average RF and **DC** power is determined over the entire measurement duration. The relationship between these two results indicates the harvester efficiency. The average RF and **DC** power levels, as well as efficiency metrics for both single-tone and multi-tone excitation, are plotted in Figure 6.6.

Figure 6.6: Average power levels and corresponding efficiency levels of the harvester. The plot illustrates the relationship between average RF input- and **DC** output-power across the energy harvester. The adaptive single-tone configuration achieves, on average, higher efficiency levels.

The results from our experiments indicate that single-tone excitation yields higher efficiency values compared to multi-tone excitation. This improvement is attributable to the higher measured average **DC** power (per **USRP** gain) observed for single-tone signals. As expected, the average RF power (represented by the black lines) remains approximately constant across both excitation modes. This consistency arises because the differences between the transmitted signals—namely, the frequency offsets and periodic phase adjustments—do not cause significant variations in the average RF channel power.

In these measurements, the total transmitted power is defined by the number of antennas and the transmit power. The overall efficiency is presented in Table 6.4.

Table 6.4: Overall efficiency levels and feasibility of the target voltage for various transmit power levels, with V_{th} equals $V_{MCU_{th}}$.

USRP		Total power [dBm]	Single-tone signal		Multi-tone signal	
gain [dB]	power [dBm]		Efficiency [ppm]	$V_B > V_{th}$ [%]	Efficiency [ppm]	$V_B > V_{th}$ [%]
75	9.1	28.34	0.8	2.5	0.7	0.0
76	9.96	29.2	0.8	2.77	0.8	0.0
77	10.82	30.06	1.2	8.01	0.9	0.0
78	11.68	30.92	1.3	11.54	1.0	0.59
79	12.54	31.78	1.6	18.87	1.1	1.93
80	13.4	32.64	1.9	27.59	1.2	14.98
81	14.2	33.44	2.1	37.52	1.2	31.39
82	15.0	34.24	2.3	43.01	1.2	50.66
83	15.8	35.04	2.2	44.8	1.2	57.34
84	16.6	35.84	2.7	53.69	1.6	57.95
85	17.4	36.64	2.7	62.08	1.7	53.91

6.3.4.2 Feasibility of the Target Voltage

One of the key questions is whether the harvested **DC** power provides sufficient voltage for the **MCU** to wake-up and stay active long enough to transmit an uplink pilot. Therefore, the initial study evaluates whether the harvested voltage level exceeds the 1.75 V threshold ($V_{MCU_{th}}$). This voltage level is measured by the **EP**. Table 6.4 indicates that at lower **USRP** gain levels, the harvested voltage in multi-tone measurements does not consistently exceed $V_{MCU_{th}}$. In contrast, single-tone signals exhibit a higher probability of surpassing this threshold, particularly at lower transmit power levels.

6.3.4.3 Estimation of the END Response Time

One of the main contributions of this manuscript is to provide insights into the response time of the **END**. Based on this information, it is feasible to estimate how long the infrastructure needs to remain actively listening for backscattered signals. Section 6.3.1.2 defined an **END** buffer of 100 μ F that should be charged to $V_{MCU_{th}}$ to transmit the pilot message. To proceed with the response time calculations, the voltage profile across the buffer must be known. Section 6.3.4.3 explains how the results from Section 6.3.2 can be processed to estimate the voltage profile across the capacitor. Section 6.3.4.3 analyzes whether the buffer voltage effectively reaches the desired voltage levels.

Estimated Time to Charge an END Buffer The buffer voltage $V_B(t)$ is calculated according to

$$V_B(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{t/\Delta t} V_{B_n} \quad \text{for } t/\Delta t \leq N \quad (6.2)$$

with V_{B_n} the voltage after processing n samples and N the number of data samples available in the **EP** dataset. The time interval Δt depends on the **EP** sampling rate. The instantaneous change in energy $\Delta E_{B_n} = P_{B_n} \Delta t$ is computed according to

$$\Delta E_{B_n} = \frac{1}{2} C_B (V_{B_n}^2 - V_{B_{n-1}}^2) . \quad (6.3)$$

Figure 6.7: Buffer voltage progression with **USRP** gain of 80 dB, corresponding to a total transmit power of 32.64 dBm (Table 6.4). For **Meas 2**, the buffer never reaches the target voltage.

The total power supplied to or consumed by the buffer capacitor P_{B_n} is defined by the harvested power P_{EH_n} minus the power drawn by the load P_{MCU_n} . The load in this application includes only the **MCU**, and is related to the supply voltage V_{MCU} . It is essential to recognize that the **MCU** still consumes several microwatts of power at voltages below the threshold voltage $V_{MCU_{th}}$. If the voltage of 1.75 V is exceeded, P_{MCU} increases and the **MCU** starts executing instructions. Based on the power $P_{B_n} = P_{EH_n} - P_{MCU_n}$, the buffer capacitance C_B , and the voltage across the buffer capacitor at the previous time step $V_{B_{n-1}}$, the voltage V_{B_n} can be determined via

$$V_{B_n} = \begin{cases} 0, & V_{B_n} < 0 \\ \sqrt{V_{B_{n-1}}^2 + \frac{2P_{B_n}\Delta t}{C_B}}, & V_{EH_n} > V_{B_n}, P_{B_n} > 0 \\ V_{B_{n-1}}, & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (6.4)$$

with P_{EH_n} depending on the incoming RF power $P_{RF_{in}}$ and P_{MCU_n} depending on $V_{B_{n-1}}$. The energy harvester output voltage V_{EH} changes over time and can drop below the voltage already present across the buffer capacitor, i.e., $V_{EH_n} < V_{B_n}$. When $V_{EH_n} > V_{B_n}$ and $P_{B_n} > 0$, the harvester is directly powering the **MCU**, keeping the buffer voltage unaltered as the voltage V_B cannot increase further due to an insufficient V_{EH} , i.e., $V_{B_n} = V_{B_{n-1}}$. Once the buffer voltage V_{B_n} reaches the **MCU** threshold voltage, sufficient energy is stored in the buffer to backscatter the pilot message. Furthermore, the response time can be estimated by calculating the buffer voltage progression. The calculations were applied to the measured data, available in [GitHub repository \[35\]](#), resulting in the representations of the buffer voltage progression shown in Figures 6.7a and 6.7b and discussed in detail below.³

Response Time Results To obtain a realistic estimate of the response time, a Monte-Carlo simulation is run with the measured data. 50 random time instances are selected from the dataset and the time to charge the buffer is calculated according to Section 6.3.4.3. Given that the **MCU** consumes power below the threshold, two configurations are considered, i.e., realistic⁴ and ideal **MCU**. In the ideal case, the **MCU** does not consume power below the threshold voltage. This specific case affects the response time calculations and shows that future **ENDs** incorporating

³It may be observed that these calculations are not strictly necessary, as the buffer capacitance can be directly connected to the energy harvester. By consequently monitoring the buffer voltage over time, similar results can be obtained. However, the proposed approach facilitates a more comprehensive post-processing analysis. Suppose the pilot message, capacitor value or **MCU** load is changed, re-running the analyses immediately provides insights into the feasibility, charge time, and response time of the **END**.

⁴The power consumption at different supply voltages of the **MCU** is measured and are available in [35].

reduced MCUs power consumption during periods of inactivity will have a significant impact on the results.

The 50th percentile (P50) and 95th percentile (P95) values for the single-tone (**Meas 1**) and multi-tone (**Meas 2**) transmission for both the realistic and ideal MCU are summarized in Table 6.5 for different total transmit powers. From this, we can conclude that *for lower transmit powers, and in contrast to multi-tone, single-tone signals exceed the required threshold values, allowing to send a pilot signal*. Furthermore, Table 6.5 also shows that *lowering the power consumption of the MCU below $V_{MCU_{th}}$ allows to reduce the overall transmit power*.

Figure 6.12 plots the CDF of the response times over the 50 Monte-Carlo measurement-based simulations. It shows, that *while the single-tone has a higher spread of response times, it also has a higher probability of experiencing a shorter response time than the multi-tone signal*. This can be understood when inspecting Figure 6.7, where multi-tone signals provide a more stable received DC power, while the adaptive single-tone exploits constructive interference over a longer time period as can be observed in Figure 6.7a.

Table 6.5: Computed 50th (P50) and 95th percentile (P95) of the END response time derived from single- and multi-tone measurements. Some configurations result in a response time exceeding the measurement time of 1 h, indicated by -.

Total transmit power [dBm]	Single-tone				Multi-tone			
	Realistic MCU		Ideal MCU		Realistic MCU		Ideal MCU	
	P50 [s]	P98 [s]	P50 [s]	P98 [s]	P50 [s]	P98 [s]	P50 [s]	P98 [s]
28.34	-	-	510	1159	-	-	-	-
29.20	-	-	418	756	-	-	-	-
30.06	-	-	206	389	-	-	-	-
30.92	620	1537	132	310	-	-	820	848
31.78	156	483	84	166	-	-	288	328
32.64	148	410	53	127	-	-	102	112
33.44	76	438	39	102	-	-	69	71
34.24	55	221	28	67	-	-	53	54
35.04	31	125	23	75	-	-	41	48
35.84	20	89	17	50	55	74	25	27
36.64	17	80	14	38	31	43	20	20

Figure 6.8: CDF of the response times for a total transmit power of 35.84 dBm.

6.3.5 Conclusion

We report and discuss various measurements at a static location within the Techtile testbed. It was found that, for the employed energy harvester, single-tone excitation yields the best results in terms of efficiency levels and **END** response time. A fair comparison was achieved by evaluating the results using the same amount of radiated power. However, it was also observed that the response time amounts to several tens of seconds to backscatter just a 10-byte pilot signal. Future work should explore the analytical verification to prove that single-tone signals perform better in this particular case. Furthermore, the measurements will be repeated and multi-carrier transmission per antenna will be considered, as opposed to the current implementation. Also, the consumption of the inactive **MCU** could be reduced, as we have demonstrated that lowering the threshold voltage for the **MCU** leads to substantial performance improvements. There is also a broad spectrum of alternative options to the pure single-tone and multi-tone signals. Future investigations could explore whether different configurations of the infrastructure and, e.g., number of carriers, could yield performance gains. Moreover, the **EP** could be enhanced by integrating the buffer capacitor, allowing for more accurate validation of response time estimations.

6.4 Measurement 4a.3 - Experimental Study on the Effect of Synchronization Accuracy for Near-Field RF Wireless Power Transfer in Multi-Antenna Systems

Wireless power transfer technologies hold promise for enhancing device autonomy, particularly for energy-limited **Internet of Things (IoT)** systems. This section presents experimental results on coherent and non-coherent transmit diversity approaches for **WPT**, tested in the near field using the Techtile testbed. We demonstrate that a fully synchronized beamfocusing system achieves a 14 dB gain over a non-coherent transmission, which is consistent with the theoretical 14.9 dB gain for a 31-element array. Additionally, phase alignment errors below 20° result in less than 1 dB of gain loss, while errors exceeding 40° lead to losses over 3 dB. These findings suggest that phase coherency requirements for **WPT** can be relaxed, and that scaling the number of antennas is a promising strategy for improving power transfer efficiency.

Objectives		Equipment	
Initial access	/	END	/
Strategies	Random-phased WPT and reciprocity-based beamforming	Energy profiler	/
Energy Measurements	RF	Spectrum analyzer	Scope MSO64B
<i>Measurements and comparisons</i>		Positioner	Qualisys
		Testbed	Techtile

Table 6.6: Measurement objectives and equipment used.

6.4.1 Techtile Experimental Environment and Synchronization Approach

6.4.1.1 Techtile Testbed

The Techtile measurement infrastructure [38] (Figure 6.9) serves as a versatile, multi-functional testbed for experimental research on innovative communication, positioning, sensing, and federated learning technologies exploiting spatially distributed resources. Modularity is achieved by constructing the ceiling, floor, and walls out of 140 detachable tiles. Each tile is equipped with a

Figure 6.9: Picture and illustration of the experimental set-up Techtile, with transmitters on the ceiling and a movable antenna connected to the measurement equipment. The movable antenna allows to spatially sample the received power over a grid of 130 by 130 cm.

custom **power-over-Ethernet (PoE)** board with power supply up to 90 W, a **USRP B210** with two antennas and a Raspberry Pi 4 for edge processing. The backbone of Techtile consists of a central server, enabling communication, sub-microsecond time synchronization and power to all tiles over a single Ethernet connection. An in-depth review on the multi-functionality of Techtile can be found in [38]. Since the publication of [38], the testbed has been extended with new hardware facilitating:

- Sub-centimeter 3D positioning and tracking accuracy thanks to the Qualisys motion capture system.
- Accurate time and frequency synchronization through **LO** distribution.
- Automatic 2D spatial sampling due to the OpenBuilds ACRO CNC system.

6.4.1.2 Synchronization Capabilities of Techtile

This work examines various levels of synchronization, made possible by Techtile's capabilities in achieving a phase-coherent system. The methods used for time, frequency, and phase synchronization are outlined below.

Time Synchronisation Time synchronization is achieved by distributing a **pulse per second (1PPS)** signal to all **USRPs** using Octoclocks. Before starting a measurement, an absolute time is agreed upon by all **USRPs**. To facilitate this, the **USRPs** participating in the experiment connect to the same **ZeroMQ (ZMQ)** server. After establishing the connection, the server sends a start command, which is received by all **USRPs** within a few milliseconds. Upon receiving the command, each **USRP** waits for a **1PPS** trigger, at which point the time is set to zero, thereby establishing a common absolute time frame. From this point forward, all **USRPs** operate on the same time reference, and subsequent commands are executed at specific times to maintain time synchronization.

Frequency Synchronisation Frequency synchronisation is achieved through the distribution of a 10 MHz signal using Octoclocks to all **USRPs**. This reference clock is used to synthesize the required clocks on the **field-programmable gate array (FPGA)** and transceiver.

Phase Synchronisation The **USRP B210** devices have two separate **LOs** to work in **frequency-division duplexing (FDD)** mode, i.e., transmitting and receiving simultaneous on two distinct fre-

quencies. In the case of the USRP B210, this results in a TX and RX LO that are not phase-locked, i.e., the phase relation between the two LO is unknown and nondeterministic.⁵ However, this phase relation is required to perform coherent downlink beamforming. It relies on the fact that the transmit and receive frontends are reciprocal, i.e., the phase relation between them is known. In this setup, the phase differences (due to path lengths and electrical components) between the TX and RX frontends and LOs are measured. More details regarding the reciprocity calibration can be found in [6].

6.4.2 Multi-Antenna RF WPT Strategies

In this work, we are studying the effect of the level of synchronization accuracy required to perform RF WPT in distributed systems. Four different strategies are considered and summarized in Table 6.7. Each of those strategies requires a different synchronization level.

Figure 6.10: Heatmap of the received signal strength (RSS) resulting from coherent beamfocussing (BF), measured with the movable receive antenna over the full grid. The power spot is approximately $\lambda/2$ in diameter (when considering a -3 dB power threshold).

6.4.2.1 Single-input single-output (SISO)

The SISO strategy is included in this work as a benchmark to compare the obtained gains of the other strategies. In the SISO case, only one antenna is used to perform WPT. Hence, no form of synchronization is required.

⁵To be complete, if the software-defined radios (SDRs) are configured in *integer phase-locked loop (PLL) mode*, the phase relation between the SDRs are deterministic due to the dividers present in the RF chains.

⁶github.com/techtile-by-dramco/NI-B210-Sync

6.4.2.2 Random-Phase Sweeping (RPS)

When the system is not phase-coherent, but provides time and frequency synchronization, random-phase sweeping can be used to illuminate dead spots. By randomly changing the phase of all antennas at regular intervals, fluctuations in the received power can be induced, yielding different levels of constructive interference at different time and spatial instances. This is especially interesting when the average received power is below the required threshold for a device to get charged. A peak in power could “jump start” the device. Multi-carrier systems are examples where the different carriers induce large fluctuations, yielding high **peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR)** signals. However, in recent studies, single-carrier transmissions with adaptive phase-changes have shown to be more promising than multi-carrier systems for **ENDs** [34].

When transmitting with the same power, the power gain with respect to **SISO** should be the sum of the received powers of all individual antennas. This is sometimes also called the non-coherent gain [39]. In literature, the gain is often expressed as $10 \log_{10}(M)$, with M the number of antennas. This is the case when the large-scale fading from all antennas to the device are the same. However, in near-field, the distributed antennas experiences different large-scale fading.

6.4.2.3 Near-Field Beamfocussing (BF)

In a fully coherent system, the phase relations between all antennas are known. Hence, these systems need to be time, frequency, and phase synchronized. In the case when the devices are located in the near-field of the system, the term beamfocussing is used, while when operating in the far-field, beamsteering is used. In the latter case, under **LoS** conditions and for a single user, the antenna array physically forms a beam directed toward the desired user. However, in the near-field, the received signals have a spherical wavefront, illuminating a specific spot rather than forming a beam, which is why the term beamfocussing is commonly used in the literature. Analogously, beamsteering acts like a flashlight, while beamfocussing resembles a spotlight. The term beamforming will be used as a general term to depict both beamsteering or beamfocussing, depending on the near- or far-field condition.

In our setup, beamfocussing is performed by estimating the phase $\hat{\phi}$ of the received signal at all antennas, through a single-tone uplink signal transmitted by the **END**. This indicates that it is the target device, where we want to transfer energy to. When performing downlink **WPT**, the opposites of the estimated phases are applied when transmitting a single-carrier tone at all antennas, yielding constructive interference at the target location/**END**. The corresponding “spotlight” will be called the power spot and will be referred to as the **BF** region or location. This considered region is the area where the received power level is not lower than 3 dB with respect to the target location. Such a power spot is visible in Figure 6.10.

When transmitting with the same power, the expected gain with respect to a **SISO**⁷ system is $20 \log(M)$ and $10 \log(M)$ compared to the **RPS** approach.

6.4.2.4 Beamfocussing with phase errors (G-BF)

While **G-BF** is technically not a **WPT** technique, the performance degradation with respect to the achievable phase-coherency case is studied by artificially applying a phase error to the estimated uplink phase. It allows evaluating the loss in gain with respect to the fully phase-coherent system.

⁷In literature $10 \log(M)$ is used, as they assume that with M antennas the transmit power is also M times lower, which is not considered in this work.

Table 6.7: Overview of **WPT** strategies, their used acronyms in figures, the applied downlink transmit phase and the synchronisation requirement needed to provide **RF WPT**.

Acr.	RF WPT Strategy	Applied TX phase	Short description	Sync. Requirements		
				Time	Freq.	Phase
BF	beamfocussing (near-field) or beamforming (far-field)	$-\hat{\varphi}$	In the beamfocusing strategy, reciprocity-based downlink WPT is used, where the phase $\hat{\varphi}$ at all antennas is estimated using an uplink pilot.	✓	✓	✓
SISO	single antenna	N.A.	Only one antenna is used during transmission.	✗	✗	✗
RPS	Random-phase sweeping	$\varphi_{AS} \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 2\pi)$	All transmitters change their phase every 10 ms at the same carrier frequency.	✓	✓	✗
G-BF	BF with Gaussian noise	$-\hat{\varphi} + \varphi_{G-BF}$	After uplink training, each antenna adds a phase $\varphi_{G-BF} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\varphi}^2)$ drawn from a normal distribution. This is used to study the effect on the accuracy of the phase synchronization.	✓	✓	±

The applied transmit-phase during downlink **WPT** is determined as,

$$-\hat{\varphi} + \varphi_{G-BF},$$

where $\hat{\varphi}$ is the estimate of the uplink pilot phase and $\varphi_{G-BF} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\varphi}^2)$ is a random phase drawn from a normal distribution with standard deviation σ_{φ} .

When the standard deviation is high, this yields on average (in space and time) the same results as the **RPS**. However, during **WPT**, **G-BF** would result in a constant received power, which could be potentially a dead spot. While in **RPS**, due to the constantly changing phases, the same location would experience different power levels during **WPT**.

6.4.3 Experiments

The aforementioned Techtile infrastructure is used to compare the proposed wireless power strategies in a real world environment. To confine the measurement size, the received power is measured in a 2D plane of $130 \text{ cm} \times 130 \text{ cm}$, as sketched in Figure 6.9. At the infrastructure side, 1 or 31 of the distributed patch antennas in the ceiling transmit a 920 MHz continuous sine wave with a transmit power of 3 dBm. Depending on the strategy, the transmitters are time and/or phase synchronized. For reciprocity-based downlink transmission, an uplink pilot is used to determine the received phase at each antenna, as detailed in Section 6.4.2.3.

The antenna at the **END** side is moved by the ACRO CNC machine in the delimited plane. The same patch antenna is used at the device and infrastructure side and are orientated towards each other. This enables repetitive received power measurements. As can be seen in Figure 6.9, the **END** antenna is connected via a circulator to the oscilloscope and **END USRP**. The circulator ensures that the transmitted signal from the **USRP** is transmitted via the antenna, while the receive signals are relayed to the Tectronix MSO64B oscilloscope to measure the received power. The exact position and orientation of the receiver is obtained through the Qualisys system.

The processing scripts and data can be found on ⁸.

⁸github.com/techtile-by-dramco/experiments/tree/main/02_reciprocity_based_WPT

Figure 6.11: The average RSS in the case of SISO, RPS, and BF is plotted at the target location, i.e., a single location rather than the entire grid (Figure 6.9). Additionally, the phase synchronization accuracy (G-BF) is evaluated by adjusting the transmit phase as described in Section 6.4.2.4. The standard deviation of the phase error in degrees is on the x-axis. All measurements, along with the median (P50) of G-BF, are plotted using scatter and line plots, respectively.

Figure 6.12: Empirical cumulative distribution function (eCDF) of the measured received power using the movable END antenna across the full grid for all studied strategies WPT. The received powers outside and inside the power spot region are plotted separately. The x-axis is limited to -80 dBm to enhance readability, although power samples drop as low as -100 dBm for the BF strategy outside the BF location. The plot allows to examine i) the gain in the power spot region, ii) the power spread, and iii) the potential reduction in received power outside the target location in case of the BF strategy.

6.4.4 Evaluation

The strategies are evaluated based on the received signals strength in the power spot and its size. Additionally, the effect of the synchronization level on the average power inside and outside the BF location is investigated.

6.4.4.1 Power spot size

As can be observed in Figure 6.10, the created power spot (BF) has a diameter of approximately $\lambda/2$ in diameter.⁹ This means, that outside of this area, the received power is lower than 3 dB with respect to the target location. This is in line with the theoretical expectation of the power spot size [40].

6.4.4.2 Effect of synchronization accuracy on the average received power

The impact on the system synchronization capability/accuracy for the received power in the BF location can be seen in Figure 6.11.

In case of a fully synchronized system (BF), the average received power is -45 dBm. This is 14 dB higher than the RPS case, which is in line with the expected gain of 14.9 dB (corresponding to $10 \log_{10}(M)$), as outlined in Section 6.4.2.3.

In turn, the RPS strategy has a gain of 7 dB with respect to the SISO case. Note that here the SISO antenna is the one closest to the target location and thus has the largest path gain.

With an increased phase error (G-BF), the received power is decreasing, moving closer to the RPS case, as can be seen when comparing the P50 of the G-BF to the RPS plot. The P50 of the G-BF allows to investigate the loss in gain when having a certain degree of phase error. As can be observed, **for low standard deviations of the phase error (below 20°), the gain loss is below 1 dB.** As of 40° , we have a gain loss higher than 3 dB. **This observation is promising for WPT, indicating that the phase-coherency requirements can be relaxed.** These observations are again in line with theoretical expectations [41]. Notably, the same conclusions cannot be made for communication, which would require tighter synchronization.

6.4.4.3 Effect of synchronization accuracy on the distribution of received power

In most cases, we want to have as much power as possible in the intended location and as low as possible outside. The distribution, and more specifically the CDF, of the received powers for the different synchronization accuracies is shown in Figure 6.12. The figure provides the received powers sampled in the full grid, as indicated in Figure 6.9. This for both inside the BF location, i.e., an area of $\lambda/2$ by $\lambda/2$ around the target location, and outside the BF location.

Observations:

- In the SISO case, the received power is higher inside the BF location than outside. This is because the SISO antenna is positioned directly above the BF location. Hence, more power is expected right below the SISO transmit patch antenna.
- The BF strategy results in the highest maximum and lowest minimum received power. “Dark spots” are created outside the BF location, having powers as low as -100 dBm (which is

⁹The measured power spot area is 0.03 m^2 .

close to the measured noise floor). On the other hand, inside the BF location, the received powers are maximized, as also visible in Figure 6.10.

- For **G-BF**, the small width of the **CDF** indicates that the received powers within the BF location are very similar in the power spot area. This is a result of the phase noise added to the transmitted phases, which broadens the power spot, effectively smudging out the power spot. This effect is also observed and leveraged on in [23].
- **RPS** exhibits a similar power distribution both inside and outside the BF region, which is expected since the **RPS** approach induces rapid power fluctuations that, when averaged over time, ideally occur uniformly across all positions. In some cases, higher power is observed in the BF region when using **RPS** compared to **G-BF** with a phase error standard deviation of $\pi/2$. This suggests that **RPS could be preferable in scenarios with low synchronization, where peak power is more desirable than average power**, as is sometimes the case for **ENDs** [34].

6.4.5 Conclusions

This measurement reports on an experimental study of distributed beamforming for **WPT**. In particular, a coherent approach is pursued. The results validate and demonstrate the great gains that can be achieved in efficiency as predicted in theory. The beam focusing capability is clearly present in the visualization of the measured receive power levels. An important condition to realize the power transfer efficiency gain is accurate synchronization of the transmitters, which poses a harsh challenge in practical deployments. Fortunately, the results indicate the promise of only small performance degradations even when having a standard deviation of the phase error as high as 40° , with only a 3 dB loss. This would indicate that the update rate of the calibration and **CSI** estimation procedure could be lowered for **RF WPT**. The current status is promising to enhance coverage and service levels for interaction with energy-neutral devices relying on RF-based **WPT**. It calls for further R&D efforts to progress low-complexity elegant solutions for achieving accurately synchronized transmitters. Furthermore, the scaling up towards more antennas and more devices to be serviced, poses additional challenges in terms of coordination, protocols and scheduling to be resolved.

6.5 Measurement 4a.4 - Reciprocity-based channel estimation

This section describes the design, build and analysis of a demonstrator for a massive **MIMO WPT** system with reciprocity-based beamforming in closed-loop operation. In order to enhance power delivery to single-antenna batteryless **END**, we propose a simple codebook-based initial access beam sweeping scheme for a multi-antenna **CSP** (multi-antenna **Long Term Evolution (LTE) base transceiver station (BTS)**) to activate batteryless **ENDs**. Once activated, the **END** is able to emit a low-power pilot sequence received by the **CSP** for a rough channel estimate. This estimate allows the **CSP** to steer the power towards the **END**, which, in consequence, is able to emit a higher power pilot sequence to further increase the accuracy of the channel estimate, and thus, further increasing the power delivered to the **END** in closed-loop fashion. The proposed demonstrator is created with a rapid prototyping approach, using an off-the-shelf **MIMO OFDM** software defined radio development framework from *National Instruments*. We provide experimental results to show the activation phase of the **END** and the positive nature of the closed-loop beamforming resulting in a spatial distribution of high received power in the vicinity of the **END**.

Objectives		Equipment	
Initial access	yes	END	/
Strategies	Codebook-based WPT, reciprocity-based WPT	Energy profiler VNA	NXP energy profiler /
Energy Measurements <i>Measurements and comparisons</i>	RF (uncalibrated), DC	Positioner Testbed	AxiDraw National Instruments Massive MIMO

Table 6.8: Measurement objectives and equipment used.

6.5.1 Channel and System Model

6.5.1.1 Channel Model

We assume a narrow-band complex-valued channel gain vector $\mathbf{c}_i = [c_{1,i} \ c_{2,i} \ \dots \ c_{M,i}]^T \in \mathbb{C}^M$ evaluated at the i -th sub-carrier of the OFDM frame, where M is the number of antennas of the CSP. We assume the channel gains to be constant over sufficiently long time intervals while the CSP and END do not move relative to each other during power transfer and no fast moving objects are present in the channel. The resulting model is depicted in Figure 6.13.

Figure 6.13: Single sub-carrier system model.

For the received symbol of the i -th sub-carrier, we get on the END

$$z_i = g \mathbf{c}_i^T \mathbf{w}_i d_i + n_i \quad (6.5)$$

where $d_i \in \mathbb{C}$ is the transmitted symbol, $\mathbf{w}_i \in \mathbb{C}^M$ is the precoding vector applied to the i -th sub-carrier, \mathbf{c}_i is the channel gain, $g \in \mathbb{C}$ is the gain applied by the END receiver and $n_i \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma^2)$ is a zero-mean circularly-symmetric complex Gaussian noise sample.

For all subsequent considerations, we characterize the END received symbol power by

$$P_{RX} \propto |z_i|^2 \quad (6.6)$$

as exact power levels are unknown due to the assumption of uncalibrated hardware.

6.5.1.2 Exploiting the LabVIEW Communications MIMO Application Framework

The LabVIEW Communications MIMO Application Framework from *National Instruments* (NI) provides all the necessary ingredients to build a TDD transmission system based on a reconfigurable LTE frame structure [42]. It contains all the needed software for the CSP as well as for a single-antenna mobile terminal (used to emulate the END) to allow for bidirectional User

Datagram Protocol (UDP) streams. This includes **MIMO** processing on the **CSP** for precoding and equalization, as well as features for power control and equalization on the terminal, so all the necessary blocks for the demonstrator can be accessed and manipulated.

First, we conceptually reduce the framework to its bare minimum so it serves our purpose well: symbol power measurement. Second, we search for possible interferences introduced by the framework when measuring signal power and detune the precomputed precoding values to implement the proposed initial-access phase and the closed-loop reciprocal beamforming. Lastly, we intervene in setting the transmission power of the mobile terminal in order to roughly emulate the behavior of an **END**, crucial for the closed-loop experiment.

6.5.1.3 Closed-Loop System Model

With the channel model shown in Figure 6.13 and the capabilities of the **MIMO** Application Framework we jointly implement the initial access phase and the consecutive beamforming phase according to the resulting closed-loop system model displayed in Figure 6.14.

Figure 6.14: Closed-loop system model.

For reasons of readability, we omit the index i , as we always consider the same sub-carrier. For the **CSP** transmitted signal, we have

$$\mathbf{x} = d_{\text{BTS}}\mathbf{w} \tag{6.7}$$

where $d_{\text{BTS}} \in \mathbb{C}$ is the transmitted constant envelope pilot symbol and $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{C}^M$ is the adjustable precoding vector with $M \leq 8$ representing the number of antennas of the **CSP**.

Analogous to Equation (6.5) we receive at the **END**

$$z_{\text{BTS}} = g\mathbf{c}^T\mathbf{x} + n \tag{6.8}$$

with $g \equiv 1$ to eliminate any possible interference introduced by the framework when measuring symbol power, $\mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{C}^M$ is the channel vector at the selected subcarrier and $n \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma^2)$ is a noise sample.

The feedback loop is closed by transmitting the pilot symbol $d_{\text{END}} \in \mathbb{C}$ with a gain $0 < \varepsilon_{\text{TX}} < 1$ yielding

$$\mathbf{z}_{\text{END}} = \varepsilon_{\text{TX}} \mathbf{c} d_{\text{END}} + \mathbf{n} \quad (6.9)$$

containing the received symbols on the **CSP** emitted by the **END**, where $0 < \varepsilon_{\text{TX}} < 1$ is the gain used to scale the **END** transmitted pilot symbol $d_{\text{END}} \in \mathbb{C}$ according to the received power at the **END**. This received symbol vector is used to estimate the **CSI** for the reciprocity-based beamforming phase.

6.5.1.4 Codebook-Based Beamforming for Initial Access

To become active and emit a pilot symbol for **CSI** estimation, a certain minimum received-power level has to be reached on the **END** [7]. Due to unknown **CSI** for unpowered **ENDs**, no optimal precoding vector can be determined. To circumvent this problem, a simple beam sweeping approach can be used to exploit the transmit diversity of the **CSP**. In our case, we set for the initial access phase $M = 4$, and generate beams according to the codebook

$$\mathbf{C}_{\text{INIT}} = \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{\pi}{2} \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \pi \end{bmatrix}, \dots, \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{3\pi}{2} \\ \frac{3\pi}{2} \\ \frac{3\pi}{2} \end{bmatrix} \right\} \quad (6.10)$$

which contains all the possible phase combinations ($K = 4^3 = 64$) with phase steps of $\frac{\pi}{2}$ while setting the phase of the **CSP** first antenna to zero (as reference). In order to apply the codebook, we iteratively set

$$\mathbf{w}[k] = \frac{e^{j\varphi[k]}}{\|e^{j\varphi[k]}\|} = \frac{e^{j\varphi[k]}}{4} \quad (6.11)$$

with $\varphi[k]$ being the k -th phase vector entry of \mathbf{C}_{INIT} .

6.5.1.5 Reciprocity-Based Beamforming

Once we find a $\varphi[k]$ able to activate the **END**, we can proceed with the reciprocity-based beamforming phase. The active **END** emits a pilot symbol $d_{\text{END}} \in \mathbb{C}$ which is received by the **CSP** according to (6.9) for **CSI** estimation. From \mathbf{z}_{END} we get

$$\hat{\mathbf{c}} = \mathbf{z}_{\text{END}} \frac{d_{\text{END}}^*}{|d_{\text{END}}|^2} \quad (6.12)$$

as a **LS** approximation of the true channel \mathbf{c} . The **MIMO** Application Framework provides the **CSI** as **MRC** weights

$$\mathbf{w}_{\text{MRC}} = \frac{\hat{\mathbf{c}}^*}{\|\hat{\mathbf{c}}\|}, \quad (6.13)$$

which are used as **MRT** weights for the reciprocity-based beamforming phase by setting

$$\mathbf{w} = \mathbf{w}_{\text{MRC}}. \quad (6.14)$$

6.5.1.6 END Transmit Power Control

In order to roughly emulate an **END**, we dynamically adjust the transmit power P_{TX} of the mobile terminal based on its received power P_{RX} to simulate different-power transmit pilots as shown in Figure 6.15.

Figure 6.15: END transmit power control curve.

We have

$$P_{TX} = f(P_{RX}) = \alpha P_{RX} + \beta \quad (6.15)$$

where

$$\alpha = \frac{20}{P_{RX,max} - P_{RX,min}} \quad (6.16)$$

and

$$\beta = -10 \frac{P_{RX,min} + P_{RX,max}}{P_{RX,max} - P_{RX,min}}. \quad (6.17)$$

The transmit power control in Equation (6.15) is determined empirically, where $P_{RX,min}$ and $P_{RX,max}$ represent the lowest and highest possible received symbol power at the **END** for a given physical setup. The basic idea is to map $P_{RX,min}$ to the lowest possible transmit power of the mobile terminal (-10 dBm) and to map $P_{RX,max}$ to the highest possible transmit power ($+10$ dBm) of the mobile terminal, emulating the behavior of a real **END**, where the transmit symbol power is strongly dependent on the power of the received signal. We want to emphasize that the unit of the received symbol power is $[P_{RX}] = [P_{RX,min}] = [P_{RX,max}] = \text{dBFS}$ and $[P_{TX}] = \text{dBm}$. The values for $P_{RX,min}$ and $P_{RX,max}$ are acquired during the initial access phase of the system.

6.5.1.7 System Flow Chart

Figure 6.16 shows the flow chart of the closed-loop system. The left part shows the program flow of the **CSP** and the right part shows the program flow of the **END**, emulated by the **UE** of the massive **MIMO** setup.

Figure 6.16: Flow chart of the closed-loop system.

6.5.1.8 Program Flow of the CSP

Regarding the CSP, we first initialize the CSP (e.g., setting parameters like carrier frequency, CSP transmit power, modulation types and letting the framework set up the hardware). Next, the program enters the main loop where each execution is delayed by 500 ms. In every loop iteration, the SNR of the received pilot symbol emitted by the END is measured. The value of the SNR is provided by the framework as the squared inverse of the Error Vector Magnitude (EVM) [43]

$$EVM = \sqrt{\frac{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N |y_n - \hat{s}_n|^2}{\frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M |s_m|^2}} \quad (6.18)$$

where

$$\hat{s}_n = \arg \min_{s_m} |y_n - s_m|^2 \quad (6.19)$$

is the detected symbol of the n -th received and equalized pilot symbol y_n at the CSP and $\{s_m\}_m^M$ is the transmit symbol alphabet.

The measured SNR is compared to the threshold SNR_{BF} which is manually set during the initialization of the CSP. This threshold determines whether codebook beamforming or reciprocity-based beamforming is used at the CSP. For the default Case ①, i.e. $SNR < SNR_{BF}$, the CSP cycles through the codebook defined in Equation (6.11). Case ① occurs if there is no active END present or the received signal from the END is too weak to obtain reasonable channel estimates.

If the measured SNR exceeds the threshold SNR_{BF} , the CSP switches to Case ②, using the reciprocity-based weights in Equation (6.13) originating from the channel estimates. The selection of an appropriate threshold SNR_{BF} is important from a practical point of view, as a low value

would allow a low quality CSI to be used for reciprocity-based beamforming, which could lead to a poorer performance than obtained with the codebook, resulting in an unnecessarily prolonged initial access phase.

6.5.1.9 Program Flow of the END

Regarding the END, we first initialize the UE by setting all the required parameters (e.g., carrier frequency and modulation types) and letting the framework set up the UE SDR. Next, we set the END inactive by setting the UE's transmit power to its lowest possible value, i.e. we set $P_{TX} = -10$ dBm. After setting the transmit power, the program enters the main loop. In every iteration, the received power P_{RX} at the UE is measured and saved to a ring buffer. The samples of P_{RX} in the ring buffer are used to determine the values $P_{RX,min}$ and $P_{RX,max}$ for END transmit power control in Equation (6.15) during codebook-based beamforming at the CSP (Case ①). Additionally, we compare P_{RX} to the activation threshold P_{ACT} of the END, which is set during the initialisation of the UE. This threshold defines the minimum received power at the UE required to activate the emulated END. If the received power P_{RX} stays below P_{ACT} , the END stays inactive, otherwise, it adjusts its transmit power P_{TX} according to Equation (6.15). This occurs, for example, if the CSP operates in codebook-based beamforming (Case ①) and finds a phase vector $\varphi[k]$ which steers the transmit power towards the END.

6.5.2 Practical Implementation

6.5.2.1 Hardware Setup

Table 6.9 provides a list of the devices used for the BS, which is preassembled by NI to work with the LabVIEW Communications MIMO Application Framework. It consists of four SDR modules, a system for synchronization and clock frequency distribution, two FPGA modules for MIMO processing and an x86 embedded host controlling the whole setup.

For the mobile terminal, i.e. the UE emulating the END, we have an SDR and an x86 host PC providing the control plane. MIMO processing is done on the embedded FPGA of the SDR. In order to move the antenna for measuring the spatial distribution of the received symbol power, an XY-positioner controlled by the host PC is used. See Table 6.10 for the full device list.

Table 6.9: Used devices for the CSP.

Name	Manufacturer	Model	Description
USRP01-04	National Instruments	USRP2944R	Software defined radio device
OCLK01	National Instruments	CDA-2990	Clock distribution device
CPS01	National Instruments	CPS-8910	Switch device for PCI Express
PXI01	National Instruments	PXIe-8135	Embedded x86 host
PXI01sl02	National Instruments	PXIe-8384	Bus extension module
PXI01sl10	National Instruments	PXIe-6674T	Synchronization module
PXI01sl09	National Instruments	PXIe-7976R	FlexRIO FPGA module
PXI01sl18	National Instruments	PXIe-7976R	FlexRIO FPGA module

Table 6.10: Used devices for the END.

Name	Manufacturer	Model	Description
USRPUE	National Instruments	USRP2954R	Software defined radio device
mimo1	Lenovo	M910s	x86 host PC
Axidraw	Evil Mad Scientist	AxiDraw v3	XY-positioner

6.5.3 Results

6.5.3.1 Measurement Setup

Measurements are conducted in an indoor environment subject to multipath fading due to reflective surfaces and objects. Figure 6.17 shows the measurement setup including the BS with the two diversity arrays A0 and A1, each consisting of 4 monopole antennas, as well as the END antenna mounted on an XY-positioner for measuring the spatial distribution of the received symbol power. The position of the END antenna is controlled by the END host software (LabVIEW).

For the measurements we consider two scenarios, i.e. two different positions of the XY-positioner where we observe an area of size 297 mm by 210 mm combined with different BS positions and configurations.

All measurements are made at a center frequency $f_c = 5800$ MHz and the LTE channel bandwidth is set to $B = 20$ MHz.

Figure 6.17: Indoor measurement setup.

6.5.3.2 Received Symbol Power as a Function of Time

Figure 6.18 shows the received symbol power P_{RX} on the **END** for the complete cycle described by the flow chart in 6.16 for a fixed position. Scenario I, illustrated by Figure 6.19a is used for this measurement.

We can observe the initial access phase followed by the reciprocity beamforming phases, first with A0 and lastly with A0 and A1, maxing out the available antenna count. For the beamforming phase with 8 antennas, we can observe the maximum achievable array gain of 6 dB compared to the phase with 4 antennas, suggesting optimal **CSI**.

We can further observe that the codebook slightly outperforms the beamforming with one array for a number of $\varphi[k]$. This is likely caused by the observation of P_{RX} on a subcarrier with interpolated **CSI**, as only a subset of the available subcarriers is used to perform **CSI** estimation [43] in context of an **LTE** downlink transmission [44]. Unfortunately, the framework does not provide means for selecting the subcarrier index for measuring P_{RX} .

Figure 6.18: Received symbol power over time for a fixed position.

6.5.3.3 Spatial Distribution of the Received Symbol Power

When measuring the spatial distribution of the received symbol power P_{RX} we consider two different positions of the **END** with different configurations of the **CSP**. For each of the two positions (points of calibration), optimal \mathbf{w}_{BF} are determined with 8 antennas. While \mathbf{w}_{BF} remains constant, we measure P_{RX} in a rectangular grid with $\frac{\lambda}{8}$ spacing centered at the points of calibration to obtain the beam patterns for the reciprocity-based beamforming case.

Figure 6.19a shows the scenario for the first measurement where the two antenna arrays are arranged perpendicular to each other at slightly different heights. The resulting beam pattern in Figure 6.19b shows a received symbol power $P_{RX} \approx -29$ dBFS peaking at the center of the grid, confirming that the **CSI** is estimated at the calibration point and that it remains stable over time. Additionally, we can observe that the beam is very narrow and that it is clearly pointing to the center of the two arrays due to the sharp transitions to deep fades possibly originating from surrounding walls and objects.

The scenario for the second measurement in Figure 6.20a shows a different configuration of the **CSP** and the **END**. The resulting received symbol power distribution in Figure 6.20b again shows a relatively narrow beam peaking at the center of the grid and pointing to the center of the **CSP**

antenna arrays. A small number of artifacts showing as dark blue dots can be observed in this measurement, caused by the loss of synchronization between **GSP** and **END**, resulting in the failure of demodulating the transmitted symbols. This behavior occurs if the antenna is moved through a deep fade or stays in a position with low received signal power.

Figure 6.19: Measurement scenario I (a) and the resulting received symbol power distribution (b).

Figure 6.20: Measurement scenario II (a) and the resulting received symbol power distribution (b).

6.5.3.4 Measurement Setup for a Physical END

We extend the setup described in Section 6.5.3.1 to allow for powering a physical END. The physical END consists of an energy harvesting integrated circuit (IC) from NXP Semiconductors which is able to convert incident RF signals to a DC output voltage. As shown in Figure 6.21, the energy harvesting IC is connected to a measurement board featuring a variable load impedance and a measurement circuit to sense the DC output power of the IC. The measurement board is controlled by a host PC via UART in order to set the load impedance and to store the measured power.

Figure 6.21: Physical END consisting of the energy harvesting IC and a measurement board.

For the subsequent measurement, we assess the following:

- Proof-of-concept setup to wake up the energy harvesting IC using the given setup operating in the industrial, scientific and medical (ISM) band around $f_c = 2.44$ GHz
- Measure the effective DC output power distribution over space with a distributed antenna setup by repeating the experiment in Section 6.5.3.3 in conjunction with the physical END

The antenna of the physical END is mounted in the vicinity of the UE antenna as depicted in Figure 6.22 in order to get roughly the same power distribution as observed by the UE (the reciprocity-based beamforming process is still done by the massive MIMO framework).

Regarding the CSP, we use the setup shown in Figure 6.23 and in Figure 6.24a respectively, where we use distributed directional antennas with a gain of 10 dBi (antennas A0 to A7) in order to mitigate the low RF output power of the SDRs of the CSP (roughly 10 dBm per port). In addition, we intervene in the precoding process of the CSP to allow for a higher output power in order to achieve a minimum received power at the physical END of -22 dBm.

Figure 6.22: Indoor measurement setup.

Figure 6.23: Indoor measurement setup.

6.5.3.5 Spatial Distribution of the DC Output Power

Figure 6.24 shows measurement scenario III used for the experiment with the physical END and the resulting DC output power distribution of the energy harvesting IC. For each position in the XY-plane, the measurement board performs a sweep of the load impedance. Having determined the optimum impedance, the actual DC output power is computed and stored.

Figure 6.24: Measurement scenario III (a) and the resulting received DC output power distribution of the energy harvesting IC at optimum load impedance (b).

Figure 6.24b shows the peak power at the center of the measurement plane (i.e. the point of calibration of the reciprocity-based beamforming weights). Compared to the power distributions obtained in Figure 6.19b and Figure 6.20b, we get a much sharper peak due to the high sensitivity of the energy harvesting IC. In summary, with Figure 6.24b we have successfully demonstrated that the setup also works with a physical END.

6.5.4 Conclusions

A demonstrator for a massive MIMO WPT system with a joint implementation of initial access and reciprocity-based beamforming is designed, created and experimentally evaluated with a rapid prototyping approach using an off-the-shelf MIMO application framework. We experimentally demonstrate the full cycle of the closed-loop WPT system with a simplified model of an END and the resulting beam pattern for the reciprocity-based beamforming case with 8 antennas, showing the high performance of the MIMO application framework. Finally, we were able to conduct a proof-of-concept measurement with a physical END demonstrating the power gains of the reciprocity-based beamforming in a real world example.

This experiment may also serve as a foundation for future implementations of more sophisticated END models and for experimenting with different initial access strategies with up to 8 antennas, as we are able to manipulate all the relevant modules of the framework.

Chapter 7

Experiment 4b - Communicating with energy-neutral devices

In this chapter, communication with **ENDs** is studied using backscattering. This wireless communication technique enables devices to communicate by reflecting or modulating existing **RF** signals instead of generating their own signals. The theoretical foundations on the two types of RF communication with Class 1 and Class 2 **energy-neutral devices** is detailed in D4.1 [32, Section 4.2].

7.1 Carrier Suppression Uplink Backscatter Communication with **END**

Our objective is to achieve uplink backscatter communication with an **END**. Additionally, we explore the **bit error rate (BER)** in different set-ups to check if this method is viable in a normal-sized room.

7.1.1 Measurement Setup

Carrier suppression bistatic backscattering is chosen as the uplink communication approach, as this overcomes the self-interference existing at larger resolution bandwidths and the low dynamic range occurring with generic bistatic backscattering. Bistatic carrier suppression backscattering requires three components in the measurement setup:

1. **Carrier generator.** A radio signal should exist at the **END** that can be backscattered. Depending on the conducted measurement, this radio signal with a frequency of f_c is generated by either a single transmitter (**SISO**) or by multiple transmitters (**multiple-input single-output (MISO)**). **MISO** allows to increase the received signal power, resulting in a higher reflected signal, improving the **SNR** and **BER**.
2. **Backscatter device.** The incoming radio signal is absorbed or reflected, depending on the data signal. To suppress the carrier signal, a local oscillating signal at f_{lo} is switched on or off at the data rate (f_d). As backscattering in all its essence is a mixing process, the data can be easily observed in the spectrum as depicted in Figure 7.1.

3. **Signal demodulator.** The backscattered signal is received by the third component, which needs to demodulate this signal.

To get insight in the **SNR** of this set-up and the influence of the distance on the **SNR**, a **BER** testing is performed. The demodulated received signal gets bitwise compared with the known transmitted signal.

Figure 7.1: Illustration of the bistatic carrier suppression backscatter set-up and the corresponding, ideal spectrum received at the demodulator.

7.1.2 Large Array and Backscatter Device

The measurements described in Section 7.1 are performed within the Techtile testbed [36]. This testbed will act as both a carrier wave transmitter and a signal demodulator. At the transmit side, 42 of the 84 antennas located in the ceiling are used to generate a power spot at the END using reciprocity-based beamforming as detailed in Chapter 6. The received backscattered signals are demodulated by individual tiles at the side of the Techtile infrastructure (Section 7.1.2).

As a backscatter device, we consider the same embedded device as detailed in Section 6.3.1.2 and visualized in Figure 6.4a and Section 7.1.2. The END has three features. It determines the modulation technique, offset frequency and the data rate (and bit sequence length). To reduce the complexity, power and cost, **amplitude-shift keying (ASK)** by means of **on-off keying (OOK)** is chosen as the modulation technique. This is more spectral efficient than **frequency shift keying (FSK)**, enabling numerous **ENDs** to transmit simultaneously, but it is more susceptible to noise. The main reason why this modulation technique is chosen, is its ease of implementation at the END and can be done with a low-power **MCU**, an **RF** switch and an antenna. In this measurement campaign, a **MCU** uses one of its internal timers to control an external **RF** switch, located just behind the antenna and changing the impedance between the harvester impedance and a short-circuit termination. The timer divides the 1.024 MHz clock by two, to provide a 512 kHz **LO** offset to the **RF** switch and therefore prevents interference with the carrier wave. A second timer modulates information at a baud rate of 1 kbit s^{-1} and sends out a 32 868 bit long pseudorandom binary sequence with an 80 bit preamble. This signal is specifically chosen for the second phase of this measurement campaign, the bit-error rate testing. A long sequence length offer more randomness, which stresses the interface more, leading to a higher likelihood of inducing bit-errors. However, they have the disadvantage of taking a longer time to complete the entire sequence.

Figure 7.2: The general setup of the backscatter measurements in Techtile with on the right a detailed picture of the in-house developed backscatter device and antenna.

7.1.3 Conducted Measurements

Two types of measurements are conducted to measure the influence of the power spot generation:

Meas 1 A single transmitter is configured to send out a carrier wave of 920 MHz at a specific transmit power level. This is further referred to as the SISO case.

Meas 2 42 phase coherent transmitters at the ceiling generate a power spot at the predefined backscatter device with a carrier wave center frequency of 920 MHz.

In both measurement scenarios, the BER is tested at different backscatter device-receiver distances and the SNR is calculated from these BERs. For this, an adaptive OOK demodulation is performed on the USRP of the receiver in a couple of steps:

1. The signal is received by the source. As carrier suppression is performed by the backscatter device, the information has a frequency offset ($f_{lo} = 512 \text{ kHz}$) away from the center frequency (at $f_c = 920 \text{ MHz}$). This local frequency depends on the internal oscillator of the microcontroller on the backscatter device and can drift. Therefore a peak detection algorithm is used on the calculated power spectral density of the received signal to get the exact carrier frequency of the backscatter device at the moment of data transmission. A bandpass filter with a width of two times the baudrate filters out higher frequency noise. An example measurement is shown in the upper left corner of Figure 7.3.
2. The OOK signal is obtained by downconverting the filtered signal to baseband and measuring the power of the signal by calculating the square of the absolute values of the IQ samples.
3. To get the actual signal, a cross correlation between the preamble and received data sequence is performed to obtain the starting index of the pseudorandom sequence. An example of this mechanism is shown in the top right corner of Figure 7.3 with the red line

indicating the start of the pseudorandom sequence. An example of a demodulated preamble and the actual preamble is shown in the bottom left corner of Figure 7.3. The sequence, containing the preamble and pseudorandom OOK demodulated bits, is stored in a separate file, on which **bit error rate testing (BERT)** can be performed.

Figure 7.3: Overview of the measured and demodulated OOK signal.

7.1.4 Data Processing and Discussion

The **BERT** is achieved by checking the demodulated OOK data with the known, backscattered pseudorandom binary sequence. This is done in two steps:

1. The received signal power of the demodulated OOK depends on both the transmit power and the distance between transmitter, backscatter device and receiver. This is why the binary threshold is set dynamically and depends on the received power during the preamble. If a demodulated OOK signal is larger than this threshold, the signal is stored as a digital 1, in the other case, it is stored as a digital 0.
2. A bit error rate is calculated for an interval of the received and demodulated OOK. This gives us insight on potential drift and makes it able to compare the two measurements.

7.1.4.1 Clock Drift and Sample rate

A first problem that occurs when demodulating the pseudorandom sequence comes from the sample speed and backscatter baudrate. Due to internal clock drift at the backscatter device, the transmit baudrate can vary in time. This results that the number of samples per symbol is not constant and varies in time. In the following measurements, the sample rate at the receiver is set at 2 mega samples per second and the backscatter device sends data with a baudrate of 1000 bits per second. The number of samples per symbol is in the ideal case 2000. Figure 7.4 shows the calculated bit error rate when the number of samples per symbol is varied. The interval at which the bit error rate is calculated is set to 100 symbols per BER calculation. The yellow plot shows the ideal case where the receiver samples each symbol 2000 times. Within 10 intervals, the bit error rate drops to 50%. The green plot is the only one that differs from the other three.

It shows that the interval-based BER only reaches 50% after Two conclusions can be made: (i). The non-coherent OOK demodulation technique is very susceptible to errors in the sample rate and/or data transmission rate. The slightest change to a higher (blue) or lower (red) sample rate increases the BER drastically. (ii). There is clock wandering (and not drift), as the BER in a later interval drops and increases again. timing error detector (TED) such as early late, Müller and Mueller or Gardner TED could potentially recover the clock and improve symbol synchronization.

Figure 7.4: Interval based BER calculation for different numbers of samples per symbol.

7.1.4.2 SISO versus MISO.

The second experimental setup tests the influence of a power spot on the BER. In this MISO case, the received signal power at the backscatter device is higher and should result in a more prominent reflected signal, improving the SNR and BER. Figure 7.5 shows the first 50 intervals of the calculated BER over 100 symbols in four measurement scenarios. The yellow, red and green line show the SISO case and the influence of the distance on the BER when a single transmitter is used with a transmit power of -10 dBm. These three plots follow more or less the same curve and even for distances up to 1 m the BER goes to -3 dB within the first 15 intervals or 1500 symbols. In the MISO case, a power spot is generated with 42 transmit antennas at the backscatter device, as depicted in Section 7.1.2. The measured received power at the backscatter device lies under -12 dBm. The blue line in Figure 7.5 shows that for even larger distances, the MISO case outperforms the SISO case. This showcases the potential of the power spot at the backscatter device, potentially unlocking higher bitrates and large range communication.

7.2 Conclusion

A demonstrator for low-power, low-cost and simple, with adaptive data uplink is built that uses carrier suppression bistatic backscattering. It is experimentally demonstrated with in-house developed backscatter device. The proof-of-concept is tested in different scenarios showing the potentially achievable BERs in real world applications. It can be concluded that backscattering

Figure 7.5: Interval based BER calculation for SISO versus MISO measurements.

with a power spot could unlock higher bit range and larger range near-passive uplink communication. These experiments will serve as a groundwork for future measurement campaigns where the use TED could be explored to improve the BER even better.

Chapter 8

Experiment 5 - Multi-user capabilities

An initial assessment on the potential of having antennas distributed throughout an indoor environment in the form of **CSPs** can be performed from the results presented in Section 4.2. Specifically, in Fig. 4.2, we can see that the difference in spectral efficiency between the best and worst user decreases as the number of **CSPs** increases (for a fixed total number of antennas). This can be translated into the condition number of the channel which decreases with the number of **CSPs**, i.e., the channel becomes more orthogonal, since for a perfectly orthogonal channel (unit condition number) the best and worst users would experience the same spectral efficiency. Moreover, it is directly related to the multi-user capabilities since, if the worst user experiences very low spectral efficiency (e.g., when the channel condition number is high) we may not be able to multiplex its data streams with that of the other users. Note that the data streams for the best and worst users may be equally demanding, so the network should be able to support a minimum rate for each and every user. Thus, apart from the trade-offs in terms of latency, reliability, and performance, if we have a fixed number of antennas, distributing them throughout an indoor environment into high number **CSPs** seems to improve the multi-user capabilities. However, we also note from Fig. 4.2 that the improvements in multi-user capabilities seem to saturate after a certain number of **CSPs** is reached. This saturation point is potentially dependent to a great extent on the scenario—e.g., on the dimensions of the room, user distribution, etc—but it should be taken into account when considering specific deployments.

Another interesting observation can be made from Fig. 4.3, which plots the spectral efficiency for varying number of equal sized (4×4) **CSPs**. It can be seen that having 2^3 panels of 16 antennas serving, i.e., leading to a total of 128 antennas, is not enough to serve the whole 128 users. In fact, the **ZF** achieves spectral efficiency close to 0, hinting that the underlying channel is ill-conditioned. However, by doubling the antennas we see that this problem is largely fixed, and having more than 2^4 **CSPs** only poses from this point a logarithmic spectral efficiency increase. This logarithmic increase hints that the multi-user capabilities also saturate after a certain number of **CSPs**, and the only gain comes from the extra array/beamforming gain extracted when having a larger total number of antennas.

The multi-user capabilities of a dense **RW** infrastructure can also be assessed through indoor channel measurements originating from the **LunCH** testbed. This allows experiments with large numbers of antennas using measured channel data. The limitations of these experiments are the absence of a dynamic propagation environment to perform experiments on. However, user mobility can be simulated to some extent by switching between channel responses measured at different points during a simulation.

8.1 Measurement setup

The measurements are performed in an office room and in its adjacent corridor area, as depicted in Fig. 8.1(a). The switched wideband distributed MIMO sounder is utilized for the data collection. Eight panels are divided into four groups each of which is viewed as a **CSP**. They are distributed in the room as shown in Fig. 8.1. Three regions are measured: the front and side areas of the room and the corridor area, as illustrated in Fig. 8.1(b). Region 1 and Region 3 exhibits **LoS** and **NLoS** conditions for all **CSPs**, respectively. Region 2 shows **LoS** propagation to the **CSPs** located at **CSP1** and **CSP2** positions while manifesting **NLoS** propagation to the other **CSPs**. For simplicity, they are named sequentially as the **LoS**, mixed, and **NLoS** regions. Equipped with a single transmit antenna, the robot moves randomly within the regions. Positions from the robot's trajectory are recorded to mimic 'virtual' closely spaced users.

Figure 8.1: (a) Photos of the measurement environments and (b) a schematic of the measurement regions.

8.2 Signal model and metrics of spatial user separability

Consider a multi-user communication system with a total number of antennas M , where N distributed **CSPs** aim to serve K single-antenna users. Define $s_{t,l}$ as the transmit signal vector in subcarrier l and snapshot t . In the work, the array gain is harvested as a reduced transmit power, which is achieved by applying the transmit power constraint $\mathbf{E} \{s_{t,l}^H s_{t,l}\} = \frac{\rho K}{M}$, where ρ is the mean **SNR** at the user side. Then the $K \times 1$ received signal model can be written as

$$\mathbf{y}_{t,l} = \mathbf{H}_{t,l} \mathbf{s}_{t,l} + \mathbf{w}_{t,l} \quad (8.1)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_{t,l} = [\mathbf{h}_{t,l,1}, \mathbf{h}_{t,l,2}, \dots, \mathbf{h}_{t,l,K}]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times M}$ represents the channel matrix, and $\mathbf{w}_{t,l}$ is assumed to be independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) complex white Gaussian noise with unit variance. The channel matrix is normalized after being obtained through the measurements. The k th measured user channel vector $\mathbf{h}_{t,l,k}$ is normalized through

$$\mathbf{h}_{t,l,k}^{\text{norm}} = \sqrt{\frac{128LT}{\sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{t=1}^T \|\mathbf{h}_{t,l,k}^{\text{meas}}\|_F^2}} \mathbf{h}_{t,l,k}^{\text{meas}}, k = 1, 2, \dots, K. \quad (8.2)$$

The normalization is performed to remove the imbalance of channel attenuation between different users while preserving the fading impact over the subcarriers and symbols. Note that the variations in channel gain over the distributed **CSPs** are also preserved. These variations, caused by large-scale fading/antenna orientation/relative position, are critical for the system performance evaluation.

Regarding the metrics of spatial user separability, the **singular value spread (SVS)** of the channels is considered. It reflects the joint orthogonality of all users, and is calculated using the **singular value decomposition (SVD)** of the normalized channel matrix, that is, $\mathbf{H}_{t,l}^{\text{norm}} = \mathbf{U}_{t,l} \mathbf{\Sigma}_{t,l} \mathbf{V}_{t,l}^H$, where $\mathbf{U}_{t,l} \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times K}$ and $\mathbf{V}_{t,l} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times M}$ denote the unitary matrices and $\mathbf{\Sigma}_{t,l} = \text{diag}(\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_K)$ is the diagonal matrix containing the singular values of $\mathbf{H}_{t,l}^{\text{norm}}$. Then the **SVS** in logarithmic units is expressed as

$$\kappa_{t,l} = 10 \log_{10} \frac{\max_k \sigma_k}{\min_k \sigma_k}. \quad (8.3)$$

A larger **SVS** means a stronger linear dependency between at least two rows of $\mathbf{H}_{t,l}$, meaning that there are at least two user channels that exhibit stronger correlations. When $\kappa_{t,l} = 0$, optimal orthogonality among all users is achieved, resulting in favorable propagation and contributing to good user separability of co-scheduled users.

The **dirty-paper coding (DPC)** and **ZF** multi-user sum-rate capacity are selected as the indicators. Assuming perfect **CSI** at both link ends, the **DPC** capacity is given by

$$C_{DPC} = \max_{p_k} \frac{1}{LT} \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{t=1}^T \log_2 \det(\mathbf{I}_M + \frac{\rho K}{M} \mathbf{H}_{t,l}^H \mathbf{P} \mathbf{H}_{t,l}) \quad (8.4)$$

where $\mathbf{P} = \text{diag}(p_1, \dots, p_K)$ is a power allocating matrix with total power constraint $\text{tr}(\mathbf{P}) = 1$. The optimal capacity and user power allocation in (8.4) can be found through sum-power iterative water-filling algorithms. The sum-rate capacity with the **ZF** precoding scheme can be obtained as the solution to the following convex problem through a standard water-filling algorithm.

$$C_{ZF} = \max_{p_k} \frac{1}{LT} \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{k=1}^K \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\rho K}{M} \frac{p_k}{g_{k,t,l}^2} \right) \quad (8.5)$$

where $\sum_{k=1}^K p_k = 1$, and $g_{k,t,l}^2$ is the (k, k) th element of matrix $(\mathbf{H}_{t,l} \mathbf{H}_{t,l}^H)^{-1}$.

8.3 Key results and discussion

The **CDFs** of the **SVSs** measured in the different regions are shown in Fig. 8.2. The average **SVSs** for the **LoS**, mixed, and **NLoS** regions are 4.6 dB, 6 dB, and 4.1 dB, respectively. Due to the rich scattering environment and the subsequent “favorable” propagation, the averaged **SVS** of the **NLoS** region is the smallest, indicating better user channel orthogonality compared to the others. Compared to the **LoS** region, a larger averaged **SVS** is observed in the mixed region. One potential reason is that the dominant multipaths in the mixed region mainly come from the same direction, which contributes to a more similar multipath propagating behavior. This results in more correlated channels between closely located users, indicating poorer user orthogonality.

Furthermore, the **CDFs** of the measured **SVSs** with varying number of antennas and **CSP** topologies are illustrated in Fig. 8.3. It shows that for all measured regions, the **SVSs** as the total number

Figure 8.2: CDF of SVS measured in LoS (top), mixed (middle), and NLoS (bottom) regions with different total number of antennas and CSP topologies ($K = 12$).

of antennas increases from 16 to 32, 64, and 128. Furthermore, given the same number of antennas, increasing N leads to a smaller SVS in the LoS region. This means that the user’s channels become more orthogonal with a more distributed CSP topology. A similar phenomenon can be observed in the other two regions when the number of antennas is small. However, in the NLoS region, when a massive number of antennas is considered, further improvements of the user orthogonality cannot be obtained by deploying the CSPs in a more distributed manner. This could be attributed to the inherently complex environment of NLoS propagation, which is supported by the fact that there is a larger azimuth angular spread of arrival (64°) compared to other regions (e.g., 37° in the LoS region), resulting in a limited improvement of the richness of the scatterers with a distributed CSP topology.

Comparisons of multi-user sum rates measured in the LoS region, utilizing the DPC and ZF precoding schemes, are presented in Fig. 8.4. At the same SNR level, the differences in sum-rates capacities achieved by the DPC and ZF schemes tend to be insignificant as the total number of antennas is increasing. For instance, at $\rho = 15$ dB, only 46% of the DPC capacity (38.6 bit/s/Hz) is achieved by the ZF precoder scheme with $M = 16$. This number increases to 85% (of 49.9 bit/s/Hz) when $M = 64$, and finally reaches 94% (of 50.1 bit/s/Hz) when $M = 128$. Similar trends are observed in channels measured in other regions, as summarized in TABLE 8.1. The results indicate that the ZF linear precoder in the deployed system can achieve a large fraction of the DPC performance, but with lower complexity.

In a multi-user MIMO system, it is recognized that to maximize the sum-rate capacity using water-filling algorithms, the base station (BS) tends to allocate higher available data rates to those users experiencing advantageous channel conditions. For users with weak signal strengths, minimal or even no capacity is allocated. This leads to large imbalances in resource allocation, resulting in insufficient user fairness and exploitation of spatial multiplexing. To investigate the user fairness of the systems, the average number of users allocated power in the LoS region is given in Fig. 8.5, using the ZF precoding scheme. It reveals that systems equipped with a massive number of an-

Figure 8.3: CDFs of the SVSs measured in LoS (top), mixed (middle), and NLoS (bottom) regions with different total number of antennas and CSP topologies ($K = 12$).

tennas can simultaneously schedule more users. For example, with $M = 128$, all users can be allocated power at a moderate SNR value (e.g., $\rho = 15$ dB), achieving non-zero communication for all users. In contrast, only ten or fewer users are scheduled in the system equipped with 16 antennas. Moreover, with the same number of antennas and SNR, a more distributed CSP topology exhibits improved user fairness. For instance, with $\rho = 0$ dB and $M = 32$, approximately three more users are allocated power, meaning non-zero communication, in a system with distributed CSPs compared to a co-located CSPs system. Comparisons of the average number of users allocated power with different precoding schemes in all regions are illustrated in Fig. 8.6. It further demonstrates the superior spatial multiplexing of users in distributed CSP systems compared to co-located CSP systems with the same number of antennas. This is most evident with the ZF precoder in the LoS region. However, for the DPC scheme and in NLoS propagation,

Table 8.1: Sum-rates measured in different regions with different precoder ($\rho = 15$ dB, $K = 12$, $N = 4$).

Total number of antennas M	LoS region			Mixed region			NLoS region		
	16	64	128	16	64	128	16	64	128
DPC sum-rates (bit/s/Hz)	38.6	49.9	50.1	38.8	46.8	48.0	42.6	49.4	50.5
ZF sum-rates (bit/s/Hz)	17.9	42.8	46.8	18.8	38.8	42.9	26.8	45.4	48.2
Fraction of DPC capacity achieved	46.2%	85.8%	93.5%	48.4%	82.9%	89.4%	63%	92%	95.4%

Figure 8.4: Multi-user sum rates in the **LoS** region with different total number of antennas and precoding schemes ($K = 12$).

the improvement with a distributed **CSP** topology is limited. These results suggest that with a given number of antennas, it is preferable to deploy them more widely to achieve optimal user separability under **LoS** conditions. However, in the given **NLoS** condition, the differences in user separability between distributed and co-located **CSP** topologies are marginal. In addition, Fig. 8.6 also illustrates that, compared to the **DPC** scheme, a distributed **CSP** system employing the **ZF** precoding scheme can serve more simultaneous users, exhibiting better spatial separability of the users.

Figure 8.5: Average number of users allocated power in the LoS region with the ZF precoder ($K = 12$).

Figure 8.6: Comparisons of the average number of users allocated power with the DPC and ZF precoders in LoS (top), mixed (middle), and NLoS (bottom) regions ($\rho = 0$ dB, $K = 12$).

Chapter 9

Conclusion

This deliverable presented several experiments and the corresponding experimental results to validate the concept of RadioWeaves in more realistic setups and scenarios. To conduct the planned experiments, several testbeds and simulators have been developed by REINDEER partners. Very tight collaborations among different partners are the key to achieve the results within the project period. The conducted experiments explore and evaluate different functionalities of the RadioWeaves technology, including multi-user capability, accurate positioning, and interacting with **END**. Moreover, further experimental analysis has been implemented to optimize the RadioWeaves infrastructure in terms of system performance, implementation cost, latency, and energy efficiency. These results confirm the potential of RadioWeaves as a key candidate technology for the next generation wireless systems and also provide guidelines for the future real-life implementation and deployment of the RadioWeaves technology.

Here we summarize the key findings of this deliverable into the following two main aspects:

1) RadioWeaves is able to perform multi-user communication, accurate radio-based positioning, and wireless power transfer with great performance. More specifically,

- Experiments 2 and 5 demonstrated that in a dense multi-use scenarios (e.g., 128 **UEs**), the spectral efficiency increases logarithmically with the number of **BS** antennas, and the system reliability can be significantly improved with a more distributed deployment of the **BS** antennas.
- Experiment 3 showed that with a signal bandwidth of 100MHz and operating at around 6GHz frequency, RadioWeaves is able to provide cm-level positioning accuracy for an indoor environment.
- Experiment 4 demonstrated that RadioWeaves is able to power on an **MCU** operating at 1.8 V with a response time of tens of seconds to backscatter pilot signals. This will enable reciprocity-based distributed beamforming with large array gain for better **WPT**.

2) There are huge potentials in improving the implementation efficiency and system performance of RadioWeaves, however, with non-trivial trade-offs ranging from system deployment, signal processing algorithms, to hardware architectures. For instance

- Experiment 2 showed that **D-MIMO** does not necessarily come with high latency. Co-design of processing algorithms, **CSP**-connecting topology, and mapping methods can provide good trade-off between latency and spectral efficiency. **MRC** with larger number of dis-

tributed antennas result in sub-ms processing latency without sacrificing spectral efficiency.

- Experiment 1 illustrated that with appropriate real-time hardware resource allocation schemes (e.g., using the concept of federation), the RadioWeaves infrastructure could efficiently serve multiple applications at the same time. It also highlights the importance in lowering the power expenditure of **CSPs** in order to have an energy-efficient system.
- In experiment 4, the importance of developing suitable modulation, synchronization, and beamforming schemes has been evaluated for **WPT**. Further studies are needed to jointly consider the support of different applications from both the system requirement and the hardware implementation points of view.

To conclude, D5.3 provides the very first concepts' validation and experimental assessment of the RadioWeaves technology. Although some of the results are initial and with certain constraint in system setups and evaluation scenarios, we believe this is a crucial solid step that approves the potential and feasibility of RadioWeaves. We hope it will also trigger more research interests and efforts into this promising area to speed up the development of RadioWeaves and **D-MIMO** in general.

Bibliography

- [1] G. Callebaut, L. Liu, T. Eriksson, L. Van der Perre, O. Edfors, and C. Fager, "6G Radio Testbeds: Requirements, Trends, and Approaches," *IEEE Microwave Magazine*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 14–31, 2024. DOI: [10.1109/MMM.2024.3351970](https://doi.org/10.1109/MMM.2024.3351970).
- [2] G. Callebaut, W. Tärneberg, L. Van der Perre, and E. Fitzgerald, "Dynamic Federations for 6G Cell-Free Networking: Concepts and Terminology," in *2022 IEEE 23rd International Workshop on Signal Processing Advances in Wireless Communication (SPAWC) (IEEE SPAWC 2022)*, Oulu, Finland, Jul. 2022.
- [3] C. Nelson, X. Li, A. Fedorov, B. Deutschmann, and F. Tufvesson, "Distributed MIMO Measurements for Integrated Communication and Sensing in an Industrial Environment," vol. 24, 2024.
- [4] G. Callebaut, W. Tärneberg, L. Van der Perre, and E. Fitzgerald, *Dynamic Federations for 6G Cell-Free Networking: Concepts and Terminology*, 2022. DOI: [10.48550/ARXIV.2204.02102](https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2204.02102). [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2204.02102>.
- [5] O. T. Demir, L. Mendez-Monsanto, N. Bastianello, E. Fitzgerald, and G. Callebaut, "Energy Reduction in Cell-Free Massive MIMO through Fine-Grained Resource Management," in *2024 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*, 2024, pp. 547–552. DOI: [10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit60053.2024.10597081](https://doi.org/10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit60053.2024.10597081).
- [6] W. Tärneberg, A. Fedorov, G. Callebaut, L. Van der Perre, and E. Fitzgerald, "Towards Practical Cell-Free 6G Network Deployments: An Open-Source End-to-End Ray Tracing Simulator," in *2023 57th Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems, and Computers*, 2023.
- [7] O. Edfors, R. Brazil, H. Petautschnig, G. Callebaut, T. Feys, L. V. der Perre, E. G. Larsson, O. Edfors, E. Fitzgerald, L. Liu, J. R. Sanchez, W. Tärneberg, P. Frenger, B. Deutschmann, T. Wilding, and K. Witrissal, "Initial assessment of architectures and hardware resources for a RadioWeaves infrastructure, Reindeer deliverable D2.1," Tech. Rep., version 1, Jan. 2022. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.5938909](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5938909). [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5938909>.
- [8] "Evaluation of the distribution of processing across infrastructure and associated requirements on back-haul and synchronization, Reindeer deliverable D2.2," Tech. Rep., version 1, 2023.
- [9] M. Attari, L. Ferreira, L. Liu, and S. Malkowsky, "An Application Specific Vector Processor for Efficient Massive MIMO Processing," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems I: Regular Papers*, vol. 69, no. 9, pp. 3804–3815, 2022. DOI: [10.1109/TCSI.2022.3182483](https://doi.org/10.1109/TCSI.2022.3182483).
- [10] I. Hussain, W. Dyab, A. A. Sakr, and K. Wu, "Latency Performance Evaluation of RF Front-End Transceiver Architecture," in *2019 49th European Microwave Conference (EuMC)*, 2019, pp. 750–753. DOI: [10.23919/EuMC.2019.8910901](https://doi.org/10.23919/EuMC.2019.8910901).
- [11] Z. H. Shaik, S. S. Thoota, E. Björnson, and E. G. Larsson, "Resource efficient over-the-air fronthaul signaling for uplink cell-free massive MIMO systems," in *ICC 2024 - IEEE International Conference on Communications*, 2024, pp. 5039–5044. DOI: [10.1109/ICC51166.2024.10622362](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICC51166.2024.10622362).
- [12] A. Fascista, B. J. B. Deutschmann, M. F. Keskin, T. Wilding, A. Coluccia, K. Witrissal, E. Leitinger, G. Seco-Granados, and H. Wymeersch, *Uplink Joint Positioning and Synchronization in Cell-Free Deployments with Radio Stripes*, 2023. DOI: [10.48550/ARXIV.2302.03387](https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2302.03387). arXiv: [2302.03387](https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.03387) [eess.SP].
- [13] R. project, "Position Estimation and Environment Learning," REINDEER project, Deliverable (unpublished) ICT-52-2020 / D3.3, 2023.
- [14] A. Richter, "Estimation of Radio Channel Parameters: Models and Algorithms," Ph.D. dissertation, Ilmenau University of Technology, 2005.
- [15] D. Shutin, W. Wang, and T. Jost, "Incremental sparse bayesian learning for parameter estimation of superimposed signals," in *10th International Conference on Sampling Theory and Applications*, 2013, pp. 6–9.
- [16] T. L. Hansen, M. A. Badiu, B. H. Fleury, and B. D. Rao, "A sparse Bayesian learning algorithm with dictionary parameter estimation," in *2014 IEEE 8th Sensor Array and Multichannel Signal Processing Workshop (SAM)*, IEEE, 2014, pp. 385–388.

- [17] REINDEER Project, “Propagation characteristics and channel models for RadioWeaves including reflector-rays,” Deliverable ICT-52-2020 / D1.2, 2023 (unpublished).
- [18] R. project, “Ultra-robust and low-latency communications and mobility support,” REINDEER project, Deliverable (unpublished) ICT-52-2020 / D3.4, 2024.
- [19] C. M. Bishop and N. M. Nasrabadi, *Pattern recognition and machine learning*. Springer, 2006, vol. 4.
- [20] T. Wilding, S. Grebien, E. Leitinger, U. Mühlmann, and K. Witrissal, “Single-anchor, multipath-assisted indoor positioning with aliased antenna arrays,” in *2018 52nd Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems, and Computers*, IEEE, 2018, pp. 525–531.
- [21] J. F. Esteban and M. Truskaller, “Use case-driven specifications and technical requirements and initial channel model,” REINDEER project, Deliverable ICT-52-2020 / D1.1, Sep. 2021. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.5561844](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5561844).
- [22] E. Leitinger, A. Venus, B. Teague, and F. Meyer, “Data Fusion for Multipath-Based SLAM: Combining Information From Multiple Propagation Paths,” *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 71, pp. 4011–4028, 2023. DOI: [10.1109/TSP.2023.3310360](https://doi.org/10.1109/TSP.2023.3310360).
- [23] B. J. B. Deutschmann, T. Wilding, M. Graber, and K. Witrissal, *XL-MIMO Channel Modeling and Prediction for Wireless Power Transfer*, 2023. DOI: [10.48550/ARXIV.2302.11969](https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2302.11969).
- [24] R. project, “Assessment of signalling schemes, protocols, and algorithms for energy-neutral devices,” REINDEER project, Deliverable (unpublished) ICT-52-2020 / D4.3, 2024.
- [25] European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), “ETSI TS 138 101,” ETSI, Technical Specification, Jan. 2023.
- [26] B. Deutschmann, C. Nelson, M. Henriksson, G. Marti, A. Kosasih, N. Tervo, E. Leitinger, and F. Tufvesson, “Accurate Direct Positioning in Distributed MIMO Using Delay-Doppler Channel Measurements,” in *2024 IEEE 25th International Workshop on Signal Processing Advances in Wireless Communications (SPAWC)*, 2024, pp. 606–610. DOI: [10.1109/SPAWC60668.2024.10694279](https://doi.org/10.1109/SPAWC60668.2024.10694279).
- [27] R. project, “Demonstrations of smart connectivity platform, support for resilient applications, and novel technologies,” REINDEER project, Deliverable (unpublished) ICT-52-2020 / D5.3, 2024.
- [28] R. project, “Signal processing for WPT and uplink signalling, exploiting environment awareness,” REINDEER project, Deliverable (unpublished) ICT-52-2020 / D4.2, 2023.
- [29] E. Leitinger, A. Venus, B. Teague, and F. Meyer, “Data fusion for multipath-based slam: Combining information from multiple propagation paths,” pp. 1–17, 2023. DOI: [10.1109/TSP.2023.3310360](https://doi.org/10.1109/TSP.2023.3310360).
- [30] B. J. B. Deutschmann, T. Wilding, E. G. Larsson, and K. Witrissal, “Location-based Initial Access for Wireless Power Transfer with Physically Large Arrays,” in *WS08 IEEE ICC 2022 Workshop on Synergies of communication, localization, and sensing towards 6G (WS08 ICC’22 Workshop - ComLS-6G)*, Seoul, Korea (South), May 2022.
- [31] R. project, “Validation of concepts and experimental assessment of key technologies,” REINDEER project, Deliverable (unpublished) ICT-52-2020 / D5.3, 2024.
- [32] C. Buyle, B. Cox, D. Delabie, B. Deutschmann, T. Wilding, M. Graber, K. Witrissal, and U. Mühlmann, “System design study for energy-neutral devices interacting with the RadioWeaves infrastructure,” REINDEER project, Deliverable ICT-52-2020 / D4.1, 2022.
- [33] G. Callebaut, J. Van Mulders, B. Cox, L. Van der Perre, L. De Strycker, and F. Rottenberg, “How to Perform Distributed Precoding to Wirelessly Power Shelf Labels: Signal Processing and Measurements,” in *2024 IEEE 25th International Workshop on Signal Processing Advances in Wireless Communications (SPAWC) (IEEE SPAWC 2024)*, Lucca, Italy, Sep. 2024, p. 4.97.
- [34] J. Van Mulders, B. J. B. Deutschmann, G. Ottoy, L. De Strycker, L. Van der Perre, T. Wilding, and G. Callebaut, “Single versus Multi-Tone Wireless Power Transfer with Physically Large Arrays,” in *2024 1st International Workshop on Energy Neutral and Sustainable IoT Devices and Infrastructure (EN-IoT 2024)*, Paris, France, Oct. 2024, p. 5.98.
- [35] J. Van Mulders and G. Callebaut, *Scripts and Data – Single versus Multi-Tone Wireless Power Transfer with Physically Large Arrays*, <https://github.com/techtile-by-dramco/wpt-signals-for-initial-access/>, 2024.
- [36] G. Callebaut, J. Van Mulders, G. Ottoy, D. Delabie, B. Cox, N. Stevens, and L. Van der Perre, “Techtile–open 6G R&D testbed for communication, positioning, sensing, WPT and federated learning,” in *2022 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 417–422.
- [37] S. K. Divakaran, D. D. Krishna, and Nasimuddin, “RF energy harvesting systems: An overview and design issues,” *International Journal of RF and Microwave Computer-Aided Engineering*, vol. 29, no. 1, 2019.
- [38] G. Callebaut, J. V. Mulders, G. Ottoy, D. Delabie, B. Cox, N. Stevens, and L. V. d. Perre, “Techtile – Open 6G R&D Testbed for Communication, Positioning, Sensing, WPT and Federated Learning,” in *2022 Joint*

- European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*, 2022, pp. 417–422. DOI: [10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit54941.2022.9815696](https://doi.org/10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit54941.2022.9815696).
- [39] J. Van Mulders, B. Cox, B. J. B. Deutschmann, G. Callebaut, L. De Strycker, and L. Van der Perre, “Keeping Energy-Neutral Devices Operational: a Coherent Massive Beamforming Approach,” in *2024 IEEE 25th International Workshop on Signal Processing Advances in Wireless Communications (SPAWC) (IEEE SPAWC 2024)*, Lucca, Italy, Sep. 2024, p. 4.97.
- [40] L. Van der Perre, E. G. Larsson, F. Tufvesson, L. D. Strycker, E. Björnson, and O. Edfors, “RadioWeaves for efficient connectivity: analysis and impact of constraints in actual deployments,” in *2019 53rd Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems, and Computers*, 2019, pp. 15–22. DOI: [10.1109/IEEECONF44664.2019.9048825](https://doi.org/10.1109/IEEECONF44664.2019.9048825).
- [41] REINDEER project, “Hardware requirements to support energy transfer to energy-neutral nodes,” Deliverable ICT-52-2020 / D2.3, unpublished (2023).
- [42] National Instruments. “Overview of the LabVIEW Communications Application Frameworks.” (Apr. 28, 2023), [Online]. Available: <https://www.ni.com/en-us/shop/software-portfolio/overview-of-the-labview-communications-application-frameworks.html#section--862789456> (visited on 05/22/2023).
- [43] National Instruments. “LabVIEW Communications MIMO Application Framework 19.5.” (Mar. 13, 2023), [Online]. Available: <https://www.ni.com/docs/en-US/bundle/377799c/resource/377799c.pdf> (visited on 05/22/2023).
- [44] C. Cox, *An Introduction to LTE*, 2nd ed. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2014, ISBN: 9781118818039.